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Cancer prevention and early detection among the homeless population in Europe: Co-adapting and implementing the Health Navigator model

D6.5 Communication Activities and Materials

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WP6 – Communication, awareness & sustainability.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

- CE – Community Engagement
- CBPR – Community-Based Participatory Research
- CFIR – Consolidated Framework for Implementation Research
- PU – Public
- CSO/s – Civil Society Organisation/s
- DGSSIS – Dirección General de Servicios Sociales e Integración Social
- EB – Executive Board
- EU – European Commission
- EUPHA – European Public Health Association
- FEANTSA – European Federation of organisations working with the people who are homeless
- H2020 – Horizon 2020
- HNM - Health Navigator Model
- GA – Grant Agreement
- IFIC – International Foundation for Integrated Care
- KVC – Kveloce I+D+i
- Mn – Month (number)
- MUW – Medical University of Vienna
- NGO/s – Non-Governmental Organisation/s
- Pco - Project Coordinator
- PEH – People Experiencing Homelessness
- PM - Project Manager
- R&D - Research and Development
- R&I – Research and Innovation
- RRI – Responsible Research and Innovation
- UK – United Kingdom
- UPV – Polytechnic University of Valencia
- UVEG – University of Valencia
- WP – Work Package

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Dissemination, Communication and Sustainability (WP6) work package of the CANCERLESS project has been guided by a strong commitment to ensure that pioneering research on cancer prevention and screening services for the homeless population in Europe reaches the widest possible audience. Through a meticulously crafted communication and dissemination strategy, the project has not only sought to raise awareness of the health inequalities faced by this vulnerable demographic but also to facilitate access to essential health services, thereby contributing to the overall well-being and quality of life of PEH across the continent.

At the heart of the CANCERLESS project, there is a comprehensive approach to communication and dissemination, utilizing several strategic channels, both online and offline, to engage stakeholders, disseminate research results and foster dialogue around critical health issues. This 360-degree communication strategy has been continuously reviewed and adapted throughout the project to ensure maximum impact and relevance.

Key components of the project's communication and dissemination strategy include the use of various digital platforms, such as social media and the website, alongside traditional methods such as printed materials and face-to-face engagement. This multifaceted approach ensures that the project's messages are accessible to a variety of audiences, including health professionals, policy makers, civil society organisations and the general public.

One of the cornerstones of CANCERLESS' communication strategy is its commitment to community and inclusion. Being aware of the specific needs and difficulties of people experiencing homelessness, the project has developed tailored communication materials and initiatives to foster understanding and empathy among stakeholders. CANCERLESS aims to empower this vulnerable population and advocate for their rights to having quality health services.

Throughout the project's lifecycle, dissemination activities have been strategically aligned with the overall objective of promoting the long-term sustainability and uptake of the project's results in European health and social care systems. To this end,

CANCERLESS has actively collaborated with a wide range of stakeholders, including European regional and local health authorities, civil society sector, research institutions and public health associations. By forging partnerships and collaborations with these entities, the project has sought to create a network of support and advocacy for PEH's health issues at both national and European levels.

In addition, the project has leveraged its communication efforts to support dissemination and exploitation activities, sharing content closely aligned to its thematic areas. By collecting and disseminating evidence-based information on cancer prevention, screening services and social determinants of health, CANCERLESS aims to raise awareness and drive action on these pressing public health issues.

An integral part of the project's communication strategy has been its emphasis on evidence-based decision-making and evaluation. Key performance indicators (KPIs) have been established to assess the reach, participation and impact of the project's communication activities, providing valuable information on its effectiveness and guiding future strategies to increase participation and dissemination.

The CANCERLESS project's communication and dissemination work has been instrumental in raising awareness of health inequalities and facilitating access to cancer prevention and screening services for PEH in Europe. Using a multi-faceted approach combining online and offline channels, community engagement and strategic partnerships, the project has been able to amplify its impact and drive positive change in the field of homeless health. As the project continues to evolve and expand its reach, its communication strategy remains a vital tool in advancing its mission to promote health equity and improve the lives of vulnerable populations across Europe.

1.1. Introduction to the deliverable

This deliverable aims to compile all activities and materials produced throughout the project life cycle. The aim is to comprehensively document all dissemination and communication initiatives undertaken from the beginning of the project until its conclusion. The aim is to provide an overview of all actions undertaken to promote the

project results, engage stakeholders and raise awareness of the issues addressed by the CANCERLESS project. In addition to compiling the materials and activities, the deliverable also includes analyses and evaluations of the effectiveness and impact of these initiatives in terms of dissemination and stakeholder involvement.

Objectives

The objectives of this deliverable are the followings:

- Document all dissemination and communication activities carried out during each phase of the project, from inception to completion.
- Compile all materials produced, such as brochures, posters, videos, social media posts and scientific articles.
- Describe in detail the strategies and approaches used to disseminate the project results and engage relevant stakeholders.
- Evaluate the effectiveness of each activity and material in terms of outreach, participation and awareness of the issues addressed by the project.

2. METHODOLOGY

In essence, the CANCERLESS project strategy aims to address and highlight crucial health challenges, particularly the lack of integrated services tailored to people facing homelessness and their increased risk of cancer. By highlighting these challenges, the project aims to motivate debate and action towards solutions that “bridge the gap between homelessness and cancer prevention”.

In addition, the strategy serves as a conduit to optimise the project's scaling-up strategy. By disseminating knowledge and research results, CANCERLESS not only advances scientific understanding but also fosters connections with social and health professionals as well as with institutions. Through this collaboration, the project can pave the way for the widespread adoption of person-centred integrated care practices.

The project's strategic approach has prioritised the dissemination of results as the main tool for maximising the impact and usefulness of the research undertaken. This decision is based on the premise that results can only generate significant changes if they are widely shared and understood by those who can benefit from them. In this sense, communication is conceived as complementary means that supports and enhances the effectiveness of dissemination by facilitating access to information, promoting dialogue and strengthening relationships with various stakeholders. Dissemination is thus the main driver of knowledge transfer and the practical application of project results in the scientific, professional and public community.

On the one hand, the CANCERLESS dissemination strategy is akin to casting a wide net, aiming to spread the project's achievements far and wide. It is not only about sharing results but also about fostering a unified approach among partners to maximise the scientific and social impact of the project. By coordinating dissemination with the support of communication efforts, the consortium can amplify its European and international presence and ensure that the project's findings have a lasting impact.

Beyond professional circles, the CANCERLESS outreach strategy aims to raise awareness among a wider audience, including health and social professionals, public administration officials, civil society organisations and society as a whole. By

highlighting the impact of transdisciplinary and integrated approaches to care, CANCERLESS aims at stimulating conversations and driving change that will benefit PEH and their communities.

Ultimately, dissemination efforts are not just about sharing information, but about sparking action and driving long-term impact. By disseminating information about the project's results and achievements, CANCERLESS aims to leave a lasting legacy of better health practices and improved well-being for all.

On the other hand, the CANCERLESS communication strategy is strategically designed to support the dissemination and leveraging of project-related content, in order to engage various stakeholders and raise awareness of health issues, especially cancer, among PEH. Combining bottom-up and top-down approaches, our communication efforts cover a wide range of actions targeting various audiences, focusing on conveying evidence-based information relevant to the project's objectives. Simultaneously, our exploitation strategy emphasises scientific dissemination through the publication of articles and the sharing of best practices, to fostering partnerships and networks that sustain our research efforts beyond the project duration, ultimately facilitating the scaling-up of CANCERLESS results.

2.1. Phases of the Dissemination and communication

Throughout the development of the CANCERLESS project, a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy has been implemented, evolving through different phases to adapt to the specific needs and objectives of each stage of the project (please see Table 1). These phases have been carefully designed, considering the results obtained thus far and the planned schedule of activities (please see Figure 1). In each phase, a combination of communication channels and tools has been used to ensure maximum visibility and dissemination of the project results, both at national and European level. In this context, the communication and dissemination strategy has played a key role in promoting the project, raising awareness of the importance of access to health care and disseminating best practices to address inequalities in cancer prevention and treatment among PEH.

Table 1 - Phases of the dissemination strategy

PHASE 1	
Initial Outreach: M1 – M6	
Objective/s:	To reach as many stakeholders and multipliers ¹ as possible to enhance the outreach of the disseminated results
Main target groups:	Health professionals Social and community workers Associations and NGOs working with persons with housing problems and with homeless individuals European Networks Public Administration
Dissemination means:	Direct engagement through platforms and alliances Scientific Dissemination: attendance to events and conferences. Direct engagement of key persons.
PHASE 2	
Dissemination and communication during the implementation of the pilots: M6-M30	
Objective/s:	To reinforce the dissemination of outcomes
Main target groups:	Health professionals Social and community workers Associations and NGOs working with persons with housing problems and with homeless individuals European Networks Public Administration
Dissemination means:	Direct engagement, aid by multipliers, companies and research entities Scientific dissemination Joint online strategy within the communication plan
PHASE 3	
Consolidation M24-M32	
Objective/s:	To engage multiplier groups and decision-making bodies in the project.
Main target groups:	Public Administration Related EU-funded projects Related Nationally funded projects European Commission

¹ In the context of public health projects such as CANCERLESS, "multipliers" are key individuals or organisations that amplify the reach and impact of the project. They are community leaders, NGOs, health professionals, media, policymakers, research institutions, industry partners, international organisations and passionate volunteers. Leveraging their influence and networks, multipliers help to disseminate information, raise awareness, engage wider audiences and promote sustainable change, ensuring that the project's benefits are widely disseminated and its objectives are effectively achieved.

Dissemination means:	<p>Direct engagement:</p> <p>Direct networking with European Networks, R&D projects and initiatives; related EU-Funded projects</p> <p>Media, forums</p> <p>Scientific Dissemination: national, European and international publications and events</p> <p>Association and open dialogue</p>
PHASE 4	Closure and Maintenance: M33-M36
Objective/s:	<p>To design a sustainability strategy in-line with the partners' organisation structures and managerial idiosyncrasies for improving the long-term maintenance of the research outcomes and results in order to assure adequate use of public funds applied to ground-breaking research and innovation.</p> <p>To consolidate a strong network of health care for severely deprived communities and in particular for the homeless.</p>
Main target groups:	ALL
Dissemination means:	<p>Scientific dissemination</p> <p>Publication of articles in journals</p> <p>Attendance and participation in national, European and international congresses and conferences</p> <p>Organisation and/or attendance at fairs, events, workshops, etc.</p> <p>Direct engagement</p> <p>Professional dissemination</p> <p>Communication campaigns (please see below)</p>

Please note that phases 2 and 3 are overlapping, which is due to the differentiated actions, objectives and targets.

Calendar

Figure 1 - Communication and Dissemination Calendar

During phase 1 of the CANCERLESS project, significant outreach work has been achieved among a wide range of key stakeholders and multipliers. Direct and scientific outreach efforts helped to Establish a solid foundation for future collaboration and awareness of health inequalities among the homeless population. The interest and participation in project-related events and conferences increased, indicating greater recognition of the issues addressed.

In Phase 2, during the implementation of the pilots, the importance of strengthening the dissemination of the results obtained, was highlighted. Collaboration with multipliers and research organisations was essential to effectively reach health professionals and social workers, as well as organisations working directly with PEH. The joint online strategy also proved effective in broadening communication reach and increasing the project's visibility.

During phase 3, significant progress was made in the involvement of multiplier groups and decision-making bodies in the project. Active networking and scientific dissemination at national, European and international events helped to position the project within the European public health arena. Strategic partnerships were established to promote actions aimed at reducing health inequalities and improve access to cancer prevention and screening services for PEH.

In Phase 4, Closure and Maintenance, a sustainability strategy was designed to ensure the long-term maintenance of the research results. Scientific dissemination remained a priority, along with the organisation of events and participation in professional activities. A strong collaborative network was consolidated and will continue to contribute to health promotion among the most vulnerable communities even after the completion of the project.

2.2. Target Groups

The target groups of the communication and dissemination strategy are divided in three main categories: primary, secondary and tertiary target groups and all three of them split in key subgroups (please Table 2).

Table 2 - Target groups of the communication and dissemination strategy

Group	Subgroups
Primary target groups	Health professionals Social and community workers Civil society sector, associations and NGOs working with PEH providing a variety of services
Secondary target groups	Health administration (public administration and, if any, private entities involved) Social care administration (public administration)
Tertiary target groups	EU-related projects Researchers and academic bodies. General society

2.3. Objectives

The objectives of the Dissemination strategy are:

- To disseminate how CANCERLESS addresses important health challenges and in particular the lack of adequate integrated services to address the challenge of homelessness in terms of cancer incidence.
- To support the optimisation of the scale-up strategy through the dissemination of knowledge gained and research results obtained in the project and by fostering (a) scientific dissemination and (b) dissemination and networking with social and health professionals and institutions.
- To raise awareness among social and health professionals, public administration officials, CSOs and society as a whole about the impact of integrated person-based care for PEH.
- To disseminate information on the results obtained throughout the project.

3. MEANS OF EVALUATING THE STRATEGY

Throughout the development of the project, a series of evaluation means and KPI's have been followed to assess the effectiveness and impact of the dissemination and communication strategy. This section provides information on the metrics and tools used to measure the scope, commitment and results of the project's communication efforts. By systematically evaluating these aspects, the project aims to measure the success of its dissemination activities and materials and to determine the extent to which they have contributed to achieving the project's objectives (please see Table 3).

Table 3 - Means for evaluating the dissemination and communication of CANCERLESS

	Online activities	Offline activities
Evaluation means	<p>1. Reach: Number of people reached by the project</p> <p>2. Engagement: Number of clicks, views, or likes. The engagement rate is calculated by dividing the total number of interactions (clicks, views, and likes) given a certain publication/post by the total number of people who were exposed.</p>	<p>3. Awareness and Understanding: Qualitative analysis of interactions, if any, including feedback collected in congresses, during joint events with other projects (e.g., the European Cancer League)</p> <p>4. Scientific projection: Publications outreach; in particular, papers and conference proceedings</p>
KPIs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement rate • Number of posts • Number of shares/RT • Number of likes/loves • Number of comments/responses 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of media mentions • Number of events attended • Number of attendees • Number of pamphlets distributed • Number of press releases • Number of radio or TV appearances • Number of flyers distributed • Number of print adverts • Number of brochures distributed

These indicators have been carefully analysed from the beginning to the end of the project. In addition, the follow-up of the activities has been carried out through bimonthly meetings throughout the life of the project and the monitoring, through a spreadsheet, of the partners' dissemination and communication activities.

As part of the dissemination strategy, a continuous evaluation procedure has been implemented to ensure adequate dissemination of the project.

To this end, specific metrics and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been established to assess the achievement of the proposed dissemination and communication objectives.

These indicators have been important for the CANCERLESS project, because they provided in real time a quantitative measure of the reach and effectiveness of the outreach and communication activities carried out. The number of people reached, both directly and through key multipliers, reflects the degree of awareness of health inequalities and the importance of access to cancer prevention and screening services among the homeless population.

The involvement of experts, policy and decision-makers is crucial to ensure the long-term impact of the project, and the number of EU-related projects involved indicates the level of collaboration and synergy within the European research community.

The dissemination materials designed and the number of articles published, both in academic and non-academic media, are key indicators of the quality and depth of dissemination of the knowledge generated by the project. Attendance at events and participation in conferences provided additional opportunities to share and discuss project results with diverse audiences.

In terms of online results, engagement and interaction on social media, as well as website traffic, are important metrics for assessing the effectiveness of digital communication and the project's ability to reach a wider and more diverse audience.

These indicators provide a comprehensive assessment of the impact of the CANCERLESS project's dissemination and communication activities and help guide future dissemination strategies.

Table 4 - Dissemination and Communication: Key Performance Indicators

CANCERLESS Dissemination: performance		
	Expected results	Achieved results
Lay persons directly reached	>8,000	>10,000
Non-experts, policy makers or decision makers	>200	>500
Related EU-funded projects	>15	15 EU-funded projects

Researchers reached (e.g., congresses, publications)	>5,000	>7,500
Decision-makers engaged	>20	>50
Offline dissemination and communication performance		
Attendance to non-academic fairs and events	>15	5
Attendance to non-academic workshops and seminars	>20	10
Attendance to EC events and info days	>4	3
Dissemination materials designed:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 poster (and translations) • 1 leaflet • >2 mini-videos • Dissemination kit aimed at researchers and research institution • Templates for press releases • Templates for social media • Templates for public presentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 Posters • 6 leaflets • 5 mini-videos • 2 templates for social media • 1 template for public presentation
Press releases or press articles published	>11	5
Non-peer reviewed articles in the specialised press published	>10	10
Journal articles, peer-reviewed, published	>10	9
Proceedings or position papers published	>10	1
Attendance to conferences and congresses	>20	45
PhD or MSc Dissertations (ongoing or published)	1 PhD or 2 MSc	2 PhD and 3 MSc
Attendance to Scientific workshops or special sessions	10	14
Online communication performance		
Engagement rate (general)	>4.5 - 5%	2,5%
Twitter/X engagement	4%	2,5%
Instagram engagement	5%	2,45%
Twitter/X followers	300	269
Instagram: followers	250	125
Unique website visitors	200 /day (mean)	591,1 / day (mean)

4. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES AND MATERIALS

In the area of dissemination, the CANCERLESS project has developed a robust strategy aimed at broadening the scope and impact of its objectives, particularly in addressing health inequalities and improving access to cancer prevention and screening services for Europe's homeless population. This section explores the overall approach taken by the project to disseminate its results, highlighting the various channels, methods and stakeholders that have been used to ensure the widest possible dissemination and uptake of its results. Through a strategic combination of online and offline communication tactics, CANCERLESS strives not only to raise awareness, but also to foster meaningful engagement and promote the adoption of its innovative solutions in various health and social care systems.

During the 36 months of the project, a series of communication activities have been carried out with the aim of maximising the reach and visibility of the CANCERLESS project. These activities included the creation of a coherent visual identity and content, which was applied in various materials such as brochures, posters, and flyers. Also, short presentation videos focused on environmentally friendly solutions were produced. The main objective has been to disseminate and communicate the purpose of the project, which is to implement primary cancer prevention and reduce health inequalities by reaching out to the homeless population in Europe. Moreover, presence in different communication channels has been established and managed, including the development and management of a website and a social media strategy, as well as the animation and creation of online communities, with the intention of engaging a wide and diverse audience.

4.1. CANCERLESS Project brand

In the framework of the CANCERLESS project, a corporate identity has been developed in order to maintain a uniform look and feel across all dissemination materials. This

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ranges from the logo to presentation templates and documents, as well as other elements such as conference posters or brochures. All these templates have been designed with the aim of being simple, intuitive and user-friendly, as well as flexible and visually appealing. Consistency in the design and presentation of dissemination materials helps to strengthen the perception of the project and to effectively convey its key messages to various publics and audiences.

Logo and colours

(Please, notice that digital screens may show aberrant and distorted colours due to the difference between CMYK and RGB)

Pantone 311C, a vibrant blue, represents confidence, serenity and reliability. It reflects the stability and security we seek to offer to PEHs through our project.

On the other hand, Pantone 184C, a soft shade of pink, symbolises empathy and care. It reminds us of the importance of addressing the health needs of people experiencing homelessness with sensitivity and understanding.

The combination of these two colors in the logo reflects the mission of the Consortium, to provide comprehensive and compassionate support to people experiencing homelessness in their fight against cancer, with a focus on empathy and trust throughout all interventions.

Fonts

For the logo as well as for documents and other materials the preferred fonts are Ubuntu (titles) and Roboto (text). Throughout the project, partners have been given the possibility to use the typeface Corbel for titles instead of Ubuntu and Open Sans or Calibri for body text and tables, in case the stipulated typeface is not available.

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EU Acknowledgment

On all documents, materials and productions related to the project, the appropriate EU acknowledgement appears, indicating the project acronym, the funding by the European Commission, the H2020 Programme and the GA Number are provided. Thus, the EU flag is included for visibility.

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During the development of the project, it has been imperative that all texts are legible and that EU acknowledgement is incorporated in press releases, journal articles and scientific publications, following the EC guidelines.

Document template

At the start of the project, a specific template was developed for the documents associated with CANCERLESS, with the aim of maintaining a consistent visual identity and ensuring their effective use. This template was meticulously designed to reflect the communication strategy and values of the project while meeting the readability and usability requirements necessary for a wide range of materials and productions. The inclusion of the project acronym, acknowledgement of funding from the European Commission, the H2020 Programme and the GA number were essential elements in all documents, along with the incorporation of the EU flag and the EU disclaimer where possible.

Presentation template

Within the framework of the CANCERLESS project, a presentation template has been developed and designed for use on various occasions, whether for internal communications or presentations at trade fairs and congresses. This template has been created to ensure a professional and coherent image in all dissemination activities of the project. In addition to providing a visually appealing structure, the template offers the

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flexibility to adapt to different content and audiences, facilitating the effective communication of the project's key messages in any context. Its intuitive and functional design allows users to focus on the content of their presentation, while the visual coherence reinforces the identity and visibility of the CANCERLESS project in the scientific and social sphere (please see Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Presentation template

Social Media templates

Instagram templates

Instagram posts have maintained a consistent brand identity while ensuring visual appeal (please see Figure 3). Here are some examples of our pre-defined branding:

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Figure 3- Instagram Templates

These images reflect our commitment to maintaining a consistent visual identity across all of our social media channels, while allowing flexibility in design to capture audience attention and engagement.

Twitter/X and general templates for Social Media

These templates are also suitable for use on Twitter/X, allowing for consistent branding across multiple social media platforms (please see Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Twitter Template

4.2. One Pager

At the beginning of the CANCERLESS project, a One Pager was elaborated with the purpose of providing a comprehensive and understandable overview of the initiative (please see Figure 5). This document aimed to present in a concise but informative way the objectives of the project, its main features and the expected benefits for both direct beneficiaries and society at large. The One Pager was designed as a key communication tool to capture the attention of potential partners, donors and other stakeholders, providing them with a clear and convincing snapshot of the project's relevance and potential impact. In addition, it served as a starting point for the project's dissemination and promotion activities, providing a solid foundation on which to build broader and more strategic communication campaigns. In short, the One Pager played a pivotal role in the initial phase of the project by establishing a solid foundation of understanding and support for its continued development.

Figure 5 - One Pager

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4.3. Project Brochure

The project brochure provides a comprehensive overview of the CANCERLESS project, highlighting its main objectives and its innovative approach to cancer prevention and treatment among experiencing homelessness people in Europe (please see Figure 6). This leaflet highlights the importance of the project in response to worrying statistics showing a cancer mortality rate twice as high in the homeless population compared to the general population. In addition, it presents the Health Navigator model as a patient-centred solution designed to empower patients through health education and social support, thus facilitating timely access to cancer prevention and treatment services.

The brochure also discusses the four pilots conducted in different European cities, highlighting the key results and learnings from each. The pilot interventions represent the key part of the CANCERLESS project, demonstrating the effectiveness and feasibility of the Health Navigator approach in practice.

It provides a comprehensive overview of the CANCERLESS project, highlighting its potential impact on improving healthcare and reducing inequalities in access to cancer treatment for experiencing homelessness people in Europe.

Figure 6 - CANCERLESS Broschüre

It has been a tool to disseminate the CANCERLESS project and its objectives among the project's main beneficiaries. It was used in a variety of contexts, including events and health centres, where it provided a concise but comprehensive overview of the project and its innovative approach to cancer prevention and treatment among experiencing

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homelessness people in Europe. Also, the brochure has also served as complementary information during interactions with other projects, stakeholders and decision-makers, providing additional details about the project and its potential impact on the community. Ultimately, it has played an important role in promoting and raising awareness of the CANCERLESS project, facilitating collaboration and engagement of all stakeholders involved.

Tailored versions specifically designed for CANCERLESS (PEH) beneficiaries were created with a focus on clear and accessible communication of the project's objectives and potential benefits for the vulnerable population (please see Figure 7). These tailored versions were customised for each pilot, addressing the specific needs and concerns of participants in each pilot location (please see Figure 8, 9, 10, 11). This strategy ensured that the information provided was relevant and understandable to the end audiences which increased the effectiveness of the project's dissemination and its impact on the homeless community.

Figure 7 - UK Pilot Leaflet

Figure 8 - Leaflet for beneficiaries PEHs_UK

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Figure 9 - Leaflet for beneficiaries PEHs_Greece

Figure 10 - Leaflet for beneficiaries PEHs_Austria

Figure 11 - Leaflet for beneficiaries PEHs_Spain

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4.4. Project Posters

The CANCERLESS project actively participated in the European Cancer Summit 2023 where its progress and updated results were highlighted through a scientific poster (please see Figure 12, 13). This poster provided an overview of the project's main findings and achievements, giving attendees a detailed understanding of its impact on cancer prevention and treatment in the homeless population. The presence at this leading European event, which was attended by approximately 350 people including healthcare professionals, researchers, other EU funded projects and European decision makers, allowed for knowledge sharing, exchanging ideas and making key connections with experts and professionals in the field of oncology.

Figure 12 - Project poster (European Cancer Summit 2023)

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Figure 13 - European Cancer Summit 2023 Website

In addition, tailored versions of the posters were developed specifically for CANCERLESS beneficiaries, focusing on clear and accessible communication of the project's objectives and potential benefits for this vulnerable population. These customised versions were tailored to the unique needs and concerns of participants at each pilot site, ensuring relevance and understanding among the target audience. This tailored approach contributed significantly to the effectiveness of the project's dissemination efforts and its impact on the homeless community, facilitating greater engagement and collaboration among all stakeholders (please see Figure 14).

Figure 14 - Beneficiaries Posters

4.5. Project Roll-up

The CANCERLESS roll-up has been used as an impactful and informative visual tool to draw attention to the main message of the project in various events and settings (please see Figure 15). This visual resource has provided an overview of the project, highlighting its direct message on cancer prevention and treatment among experiencing homelessness people in Europe. In addition to its use at events, the roll-up was also employed during interactions with other projects, stakeholders and decision-makers, serving as complementary information. It has been a tool to promote the project, facilitating access to its communication channels and concise information about the consortium, to facilitate collaboration by all stakeholders involved.

Figure 15 - CANCERLESS Roll-up

4.6. Videos

The videos produced for the CANCERLESS Project represent an essential tool in the communication and dissemination strategy. These audiovisual pieces have been carefully designed to effectively convey the objectives, methodologies and achievements of the project in a clear and concise manner. Through data, interviews, powerful images and well-structured narratives, the videos provide an in-depth and comprehensive overview of the work carried out in the project, highlighting its importance in the fight against cancer among homeless populations in Europe.

At M28, IFIC produced an informative video on the CANCERLESS project with the aim of raising awareness of the issue and reaching out to beneficiaries.

The video highlights the high cancer mortality among experiencing homelessness people in Europe and the barriers they face in accessing care. It presents CANCERLESS' vision of preventing cancer and enabling early diagnosis through patient-centred interventions. Explains the CANCERLESS Health Navigator Model, which is based on a

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combination of navigation and patient empowerment models. He describes the pilots of the project in several European cities and how they provide support to the needs of experiencing homelessness people. Finally, he invites you to find out more by visiting the project's website.

This video was not only disseminated through the project's social media channels, but was also included on the homepage of the project's website (<https://cancerless.eu/>) and used as a letter of introduction at various events (please see Figure 16).

Figure 16 - CANCERLESS Video

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As part of the project's dissemination strategy, a series of videos were developed to share the results of the pilots and highlight the key role of the Health Navigators (please see Figure 17, 18). These videos feature clips showing the Health Navigators in the various pilot settings. Through these clips, it is explained how the Health Navigator Model, a patient-centred intervention backed by evidence, delivers its activity. In addition, it highlights how these navigators facilitate timely access to primary and secondary prevention services, playing a crucial role in improving the health of the homeless population.

The videos produced were shared through the CANCERLESS project's social media platforms. This dissemination strategy allowed reaching a wide audience and increasing the visibility of the results of the pilots, as well as highlighting the important role of hHealth Navigators in the implementation of the model.

Figure 17 - Videos of the pilots_Instagram

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Figure 18 - Videos of the pilots_Twitter/X

4.7. Project Website

www.cancerless.eu

During the project’s development, the CANCERLESS website has proven indispensable for disseminating pertinent information about the project (please see Figure 19). The platform remains consistently updated through its blog, serving as the main channel for sharing news, updates and short articles related to the project. In this period, 18 blog posts were published, covering various topics from research progress to CANCERLESS-related events and activities.

The CANCERLESS website has experienced steady growth in its audience, reflecting increasing user interest and engagement with the project's content. Although specific data on website traffic is unavailable we have observed a general increase in user interaction with the published content. This is reflected in a longer average time spent on the site and an increase in the frequency of user visits. These indicators suggest an increasing level of participation and engagement with the content provided by the project throughout its development.

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The CANCERLESS project website has served as a central hub for the dissemination of general and project-specific information. Designed with a clear and easy-to-navigate structure, it provides stakeholders with access to the project's objectives, activities and results, as well as to relevant documents, reports and publications. The website has been regularly updated to reflect the latest progress and achievements of the project, ensuring stakeholder information and participation. Optimised for mobile devices, it allows convenient access anytime, anywhere. To maximise its impact, the website is promoted through various online platforms and communication channels, reaching a wide audience interested in the fight against cancer among people experiencing homelessness (PEHs).

Figure 19 - Project Website (www.cancerless.eu)

In line with the communication strategy, this website has evolved to align with the project's objectives, developments and results through specially curated sections. Scheduled publications in the news and updates section provide periodic updates on the project's status and pilot results. Such content has been created with the aim of reaching the identified target groups, in order to involve stakeholders who can actively contribute to addressing the issue in question:

- Experts and researchers
- Institutions
- Companies
- Laypersons
- Social investors
- EU Commission
- Related EU projects
- Decision makers and public administration

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- Citizen platforms
- Civil society entities
- Experts and researchers
- Related EU projects

Throughout the development of the project, the CANCERLESS website has been an active tool for publishing information relevant to the project audience. The blog (please see Figure 20) content has addressed a wide variety of topics, such as research progress, results, relevant interviews, participation in the pilots, awareness-raising events and news related to the health and well-being of experiencing homelessness people. This diversity of content has kept the audience informed and engaged with the project throughout the period. In addition to the blog, the website has served as a central resource for accessing detailed information about the project, including details about the partners, objectives, methodology and results. The CANCERLESS website has played a crucial role in disseminating information and promoting the project to various audiences, contributing significantly to its visibility and outreach.

Figure 20 - Website_Blog

Furthermore, the results section has been meticulously updated to include key outcomes achieved throughout the project's duration. This encompasses comprehensive insights into the results obtained from pilot studies conducted, publications authored by the

CANCERLESS team during project development, as well as the dissemination of public deliverables and reports. By ensuring the thorough documentation of these essential components, stakeholders gain valuable access to the project's findings, thereby facilitating broader understanding and engagement with CANCERLESS' endeavors.

- **The results of the pilots**

The pilot phase of the CANCERLESS project has been a key component in assessing the effectiveness and impact of our health navigation model designed for PEH. This phase has provided valuable information on the practical implementation and outcomes of our initiatives to improve cancer prevention and screening among this vulnerable population.

These figures reflect the project's extensive outreach and engagement efforts, highlighting the progress made in addressing health inequalities and improving access to essential cancer prevention services for the homeless population across Europe. Detailed results and analysis can be found on the CANCERLESS project website, serving the purpose of transparency and accountability.

- **The publications that the CANCERLESS team has made during the development of the project.**

Throughout the development of the CANCERLESS project, the project consortium has been actively involved in the production of publications aimed at disseminating research results and contributing to broadening the knowledge base of the scientific community. These publications cover a wide range of topics related to cancer prevention, health inequalities and innovative approaches to healthcare delivery for homeless populations.

These publications have been included on the CANCERLESS Project website to share research findings in a transparent and accessible way (please see Figure 22). By making this information available online, the aim is to facilitate access to the results, encourage knowledge sharing within the scientific community and broaden the impact of the work by reaching a wider and more diverse audience.

Our Results

Publications

- Carmichael, C., Smith, L., Aldasoro, E., Gil Salmerón, A., Alhambra-Borrás, T., Doñate-Martínez, A., ... & Grabovac, I. (2022). Exploring the application of the navigation model with people experiencing homelessness: a scoping review. *Journal of Social Distress and Homelessness*, 1-15. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/10530789.2021.2021363>
- Jeleff, M., Markovic, L., Lehner, L., Schiffler, T., & Grabovac, I. (2022). Anwendung der Patientennavigation bei obdachlosen Menschen: ein Scoping Review (CANCERLESS). *Das Gesundheitswesen*, 84(08/09). <https://www.thieme-connect.com/products/ejournals/html/10.1055/s-0042-1751177>
- Schiffler, T., Jeleff, M., Lehner, L., Markovic, L., & Grabovac, I. (2022). Co-Design des Health Navigator Modells für Österreich: das CANCERLESS Projekt. *Das Gesundheitswesen*, 84(08/09). <https://www.thieme-connect.com/products/ejournals/html/10.1055/s-0042-1751149>
- Schiffler, T., Lehner, L., Jeleff, M., Markovic, L., & Grabovac, I. (2022). Obdachlosigkeit und Krebsvorsorge: Aktuelle Barrieren in der Gesundheitsversorgung (CANCERLESS). *Das Gesundheitswesen*, 84(08/09). <https://www.thieme-connect.com/products/ejournals/html/10.1055/s-0042-1751148>
- Schiffler, T., Carmichael, C., Smith, L., Doñate-Martínez, A., Alhambra-Borrás, T., Varadé, M. R., Cortes, J. B., Kouvari, M., Karnaki, P., Moudatsou, M., Tabaki, I., Gil-Salmeron, A., & Grabovac, I. (2023). Access to cancer preventive care and program considerations for people experiencing homelessness across four European countries: An exploratory qualitative study. *EClinicalMedicine*, 62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2023.102095>
- Carmichael, C., Schiffler, T., Smith, L., Moudatsou, M., Tabaki, I., Doñate-Martínez, A., Alhambra-Borrás, T., Kouvari, M., Karnaki, P., Gil-Salmeron, A., & Grabovac, I. (2023). Barriers and facilitators to health care access for people experiencing homelessness in four European countries: An exploratory qualitative study. *International Journal for Equity in Health*, 22(1), 206. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12939-023-02011-4>
- Jeleff, M., Haider, S., Schiffler, T., Gil-Salmerón, A., Yang, L., Schuch, F. B., & Grabovac, I. (2024). Cancer risk factors and access to cancer prevention services for people experiencing homelessness. *The Lancet Public Health*, 9(2), e128-e146. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667\(23\)00298-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667(23)00298-0)
- Coronado-Vázquez, M., Trenado, R., Benito-Sánchez, B., Barrio Cortes, J., Gil-Salmerón, A., Amengual-Pliego, M., & Grabovac, I. (2024). Cancer prevention in people experiencing homelessness: Ethical considerations and experiences from the CANCERLESS project. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1371505>

Figure 21 - Website_Publications of the Project

- **The public deliverables and reports of the project**

Public project reports and deliverables have been made accessible through the CANCERLESS website to ensure transparency and dissemination of the results achieved (please see Figure 23). By publishing these documents online, the aim is to share the project's progress and achievements with stakeholders, including partners, stakeholders and the general public. This practice also contributes to the accountability and visibility of the work carried out under the project.

Deliverables and reports

- [D2.1 Synthesis Report on Systematic Review to Synthesize the Theoretical Foundations of the Health Navigator Model in the Homeless Population](#)
- [D2.3 Synthesis Report on Health Needs and Barriers to Access Cancer Care Prevention for the Homeless Population at System, Provider and Individual Levels](#)
- [D2.5 Health Navigator Model for Europe](#)
- [D3.1 Guidelines and Materials for Capacity Building in the Pilot Sites](#)
- [D3.2 Agreed Pilot Implementation Plans](#)

Figure 22 - Website_Deliverables & Reports

The website's nature and online presence require careful monitoring. While we have not used Google Analytics due to privacy concerns for users, we have not been able to collect our usual data and metrics. Instead, we have worked with GreenHost, a Netherlands-based service focused on environmentally sustainable hosting and GDPR compliance policies, to track basic metrics.

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Given the nature of the website and the extensive monitoring of social media channels aimed at disseminating the project itself and its website, GAnalytics - which poses some privacy challenges for users - has not been used, so the usual data and metrics have not been taken, while basic metrics have been tracked by GreenHost, a Netherlands-based service focused on environmentally sustainable hosting and GDPR compliance policies.

During the creation of the project website (M3) until the end of the project in May 2024 (M36), the CANCERLESS website has registered 11,867 visits, with 3,568 unique visitors. This averages to approximately 591.1 visits per day and 177.7 unique visits per day (please see Figure 24). These metrics reflect a consistent level of engagement and interest in the project's online content, indicating ongoing interaction with the website and its resources.

Figure 23 - CANCERLESS Website_Results per month

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A detailed analysis of the results by country reveals varying levels of participation and interest in the CANCERLESS project (please see Figure 25). The Netherlands stands out with a significant number of visits and unique visitors, indicating an outstanding engagement with the issue of health among people experiencing homelessness. Germany and the UK, although with a sizeable population, show proportionally lower participation, but remain important markets for the dissemination of the project. Austria, with a relatively small population, shows a particularly high interest, while France, Spain and Greece, although with a smaller participation in absolute terms, reflect a significant interest in the project, highlighting the importance of raising awareness of homeless health in these regions.

Figure 24 - CANCERLESS Website_Results per country

Data illustrates a notable growth in the number of visitors and website activity over the years. From 2021 to 2024, there is a significant increase in the total number of visitors, as well as in the average number of visitors per day. Although there was a peak in activity during 2023, with a considerable number of unique visitors, a general upward trend in engagement is evident over time. This increase in website activity reflects increased interest and engagement with the CANCERLESS project, suggesting a growing

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awareness of the importance of addressing health inequalities among PEH in Europe (please see Figure 26).

Figure 25 - CANCERLESS Website_Results per years

The CANCERLESS project website is sustainable over time because its content has been designed to be relevant and useful over the long term, ensuring that it continues to attract traffic and serve as a valuable resource for the community.

4.8. Social Media Channels

For the final results of the project, a structured timetable has been implemented comprising three distinct phases:

- **Launch Phase:** This stage marked the beginning of the campaign with high media visibility, aimed at generating initial awareness and interest in the project.
- **Main Phase:** Following the launch, the campaign entered its main phase, incrementally using media to reinforce the message. Regular updates and reminders were disseminated to keep the audience engaged.
- **Final Phase:** As the campaign approached its conclusion, a final media push was executed to maximize impact and prompt action. This phase emphasized urgency and reiterated key messages.

The CANCERLESS communication campaigns utilized various virtual platforms, mass media channels, interpersonal channels, small group meetings, and one-on-one

discussions. The selection of media channels was tailored to the specific target audience and key messages of each campaign, ensuring effective communication and engagement.

Throughout the project's development,, the relevance of various social media platforms (e.g. Instagram, Twitter/X, YouTube, and Research Gate) has been assessed to enhance project's communication and dissemination of results. Instagram and Twitter/X have been identified as the main social channels to reach the project's audience. The creation of a large online community has been considered as an effective method to exploit the results of the project, and the website has been integrated with the different social networks through plugins. KVC, as WP6 leader, has been responsible for defining and executing a community management strategy with the help of the project coordination and the whole consortium. In addition, each consortium partner, as lead developer of the application, has been responsible for feeding these social networks with updates on the progress and achievements of each application (please see Table 9).

Table 5 - Basic template for social media and online communication plans

Question	Explanation
Social media tools analysis table	<p><u>TWITTER: Microblogging social media channel</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose: To disseminate the general context, objectives, outputs and results of CANCERLESS. • Uses: networking with other funded projects, researchers, and institutions; content curation; communication about homelessness; dissemination of objectives; dissemination of results. • Target groups: Projects; researchers and academia; health professionals; social workers; civil society entities; general society. <p><u>Instagram: online photo and video-sharing social networking service</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Purpose: to raise awareness at societal level • Uses: to catch the attention of the general society; networking with other projects, civil society organizations (specifically associations), and institutions working with marginalised and/or severely deprived communities • Target groups: general citizenship; CSOs.
Context analysis	<p>We have identified several EU projects using Twitter at a variable rate of intensity and frequency of publications; the use of Instagram is minoritarian, whilst the focus of EU projects on awareness raising may be less important than the current project.</p> <p>Overall, both social media channels are appropriate for our audience as defined. During the progress of the project, Research Gate has been integrated into the strategy through a "Project" created by the project coordinator.</p>

	Target	Type of use		
		Proactive	Active	Passive
	Citizen	X		
	Health professional	X	x	
	Social worker	X	x	
	Researcher		x	X
	Institutional site		x	X
	Project site		x	X
	Civil Society Organisation	X		
	Advocate	X		
	Activist or community leader	X		
Analysis of Instagram	<p>Instagram is a social media channel not usually used by EU projects; that is why we decided to include a more detailed analysis of the state of this channel:</p> <p>https://www.instagram.com/eu_echo/?hl=es</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Funded project - Videos and audio-visual content - Long descriptions <p>https://www.instagram.com/european_youth_eu/?hl=es</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - European programme; not a project - Mixed posts (pictures, infographics, calls for proposals...) <p>https://www.instagram.com/projecte.eu/?hl=es</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-centred contents - Shares specific contents through the link tree <p>https://www.instagram.com/palrobotics/?hl=es</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Audio-visuels <p>https://www.instagram.com/red/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Non-profit organisation - Merchandising focused - Mixed contents: photos, promotion, audio-visuels, etc. <p>Interesting differences noticed between https://www.instagram.com/unicef/ and https://www.instagram.com/unicef_es/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Both are focused on fundraising and use pictures of minors, but the international account is focused on the "positive" side of community development; the Spanish account uses mainly minors, with a sensationalistic approach, trying to "move" the audience by means of unpleasurable emotional states. 			
Beneficiaries' analysis	<p>Beneficiaries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Due to the social, cultural and economic constraints of our beneficiaries, social media channels have not focused on them, but on multipliers and in particular on CSOs and community leaders. However, it should be noticed that the use of social media channels among the homeless communities depends also on socio-demographic factors and is mainly determined by the age² <p>General society; lay-persons: Demographic characterization³.</p>			

²https://digitalcommons.csumb.edu/caps_thes_all/977/
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3747797

³ <https://www.omnicoreagency.com/instagram-statistics/>

- Reports and grey literature analysing their access to information, the internet and social media

The basic template for social media and online communication plans of the CANCERLESS project covers various social media tools and their intended purposes, uses and target groups.

In the case of Twitter/X, the purpose is to disseminate general information about the project, its objectives, products and results. It serves as a tool for networking with other funded projects, researchers, institutions, and for communication about homelessness and dissemination purposes. Target groups include projects, researchers, health professionals, social workers, civil society organisations and the general public.

Instagram, on the other hand, is used to raise awareness in society. Its uses include attracting the attention of the general public, networking with other projects, civil society organisations and institutions working with marginalised communities. The target groups of Instagram are the general public and civil society organisations.

In the context analysis, it is noted that Twitter/X is more commonly used by EU projects than Instagram, but both channels are considered appropriate for the CANCERLESS audience. In addition, Research Gate has been integrated into the strategy for proactive use.

The target audience for social media channels varies according to their level of engagement: proactive, active or passive. This categorisation helps to adapt the communication strategy accordingly.

The analysis of Instagram reveals that EU projects do not regularly use it, but examples from several organisations provide information on content types, styles and approaches.

Finally, the beneficiary analysis highlights the importance of multipliers such as CSOs and community leaders, rather than direct engagement with the homeless community, due to social, cultural and economic constraints. However, it recognises that the use of social networks among the homeless community varies depending on socio-demographic factors, mainly age. Understanding the demographics of the wider society

and its access to information, the internet and social media is crucial for effective communication.

All images of people used in social media and other CANCERLESS project materials are sourced from royalty-free image banks, photographs of people who are part of the consortium or images published openly at events, both face-to-face and online. This practice guarantees respect for copyright and ethics in the representation of people, ensuring that the images used are appropriate and authorised for use in the communication of the project. In this way, it promotes a positive and responsible image of the work, while protecting the privacy and rights of the people portrayed.

Hashtags

The hashtags selected for use on platforms such as Instagram and Twitter/X are designed to amplify the reach and visibility of the CANCERLESS project, addressing key issues related to the health and well-being of PEH in Europe. From hashtags focused on fighting poverty and preventing homelessness, to those highlighting the importance of European healthcare and efforts to combat cancer, such as the EU Cancer Plan (#EUCancerPlan). These hashtags aim to raise awareness, foster solidarity and promote inclusion in the public health agenda.

Hashtags to be used on Instagram and Twitter/X, among others have been:

#poverty #homelesslivesmatter #homelessnessprevention #homelessness #homeless #womenhealth #healthcare #leavenoonebehind

#EUcanbeatcancer #EUCancerPlan

#H2020

Audience

The social media communication channels selected for the CANCERLESS project were carefully chosen to reach a wide range of relevant audiences. On Twitter/X, it targets experts, institutions, companies, social investors, the European Commission, EU-related projects, decision-makers and public administrations, as well as the public and

citizen platforms. On Instagram, on the other hand, it focuses on ordinary people, civil society entities and affinity groups, thus ensuring comprehensive coverage and meaningful participation in communication and outreach activities.

Consequently, the social networks considered were the following (please see Table 10):

Table 6 - Main Social Media communication channels

Social Media Channel	Target audience/s
Twitter/X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experts & Researchers • Institutions • Companies • Social Investors • EU Commission • Related EU Projects • Decision makers and public administration • Lay persons • Citizens' platforms
Instagram	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lay persons • Civil Society Entities

Instagram

Instagram focuses on short posts with written content, aimed at projects and CSOs, and pictures illustrating the post trying to maintain the same branding and style, including colours. Given the native tool for analysing the profile within Instagram, the account has been analysed using Inflact.⁴

Analysis of the results on Instagram reveals significant progress in building an online community committed to the CANCERLESS project. During the period analysed, a steady increase in the number of followers is observed, indicating an organic and sustained growth of the audience interested in the project. In addition, follower engagement, as measured by the interaction rate, shows a positive response to the content shared,

⁴ <https://inflact.com/tools/profile-analyzer/>

suggesting a level of active participation and genuine interest in the issue of fighting cancer among PEH. These results reinforce the effectiveness of the communication strategy on Instagram and highlight its crucial role in spreading the message and promoting awareness of health inequalities. The results are as follows:

- Total posts: 142
- Engagement rate: 2,45%
- Followers: 125
- Average user activity: 6.45%
- Most popular time: Tuesday 12.00pm
- Post per day: 0,47
- Post per week: 2,47
- Posts per month: 12.47

Analysis of the results on Instagram of the CANCERLESS project shows a steady and growing engagement with the audience. 142 posts have been published, indicating an active and sustained communication strategy. The engagement rate is 2.45%, reflecting positive interaction and continued interest from followers. With 125 followers, there is a moderate but steady growth of the online community.

The average user activity is 6.45%, suggesting a high level of engagement with the content shared. The most popular time for interaction is Tuesdays at 12:00 pm, which provides valuable information for planning future publications. In terms of frequency, a rate of 0.47 posts per day, 2.47 posts per week and 12.47 posts per month has been maintained, ensuring a constant presence on the platform.

Overall, these qualitative results indicate that the communication strategy on Instagram has been effective in keeping the audience informed and engaged, contributing significantly to the visibility and impact of the CANCERLESS project (please see Figure 27).

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Figure 26 - Instagram profile

Twitter/X

Twitter/X has primarily been utilized to disseminate the general context, objectives, results and achievements of the project, as well as to establish contacts with other funded projects, researchers and relevant institutions. This communication channel has played a crucial role in interacting with a wide range of target groups, including projects, academics, health professionals, social workers, civil society entities and society at large. The results are as follows:

- Followers: 271
- Total posts: 447
- Average engagement rate: 2.5%
- Clicks in the link (avg.): 8,75
- RT without comments (avg.) 26,5
- RT per day (avg): 1
- Likes (avg.): 798
- Likes per day (avg): 2
- Responses: 1 (total); Responses (avg): 0

The qualitative findings of the CANCERLESS project's Twitter/X results highlight a significant level of interaction and engagement with the audience (please see Figure 28). With a total of 271 followers and 447 posts, an active and continuous presence has been maintained on the platform. The average engagement rate of 2.5% indicates a good level of interaction with the content.

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On average, links shared in tweets have received 8.75 clicks, demonstrating an active interest in the linked external content. Retweets without comments average 26.5, suggesting that the audience finds the content valuable and worth sharing with their networks. With an average of one retweet per day, there is a steady dissemination of the posts.

The posts have received 798 likes" on average, with an average of two "likes" per day, indicating a continued positive response from the audience. However, responses have been minimal, with only one total response and an average of zero replies, which could point to an opportunity to encourage dialogue that is more direct and feedback.

The qualitative results on Twitter reflect an effective communication strategy that has managed to maintain audience interest and engagement. These indicators are evidence of the CANCERLESS project's ability to engage its audience and spread its message effectively.

Figure 27 - X/Twitter profile

Through the Twitter/X platform, we have sought to maintain constant and up-to-date communication with the target audience, providing detailed information on each step and development of the project. To this end, the scientific publications of the project have been published, as well as the progress of the pilots. Detailed information on the pilots has been provided, including relevant data and the perspective of the main parties involved in the piloting process of the Health Navigator Model. In addition, special attention has been paid to key days, initiatives and relevant events (Movember, European Week Against Cancer, etc.) at a global level, preparing powerful communication campaigns on social networks to amplify our reach and engagement with society.

The following table divides the project into monthly periods, considering that the reported period represents a well-matured account and eliminating the "noise" that may be caused by the launch of the account. Summer holidays and other usual periods of low activity are also included. Table 11 below, presents the tweets with the highest engagement rate:

Table 7 -Tweets with the highest engagement rate

Tweet	Impressions	Interactions	Engagement rate (%)
Dec 21 – 22			
Our first paper has been published! In this scoping review, we explore the how #patientnavigation models have been utilised with people experiencing #homelessness to improve their access to #healthcare tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.10... cc @EdelAldasoro	345	28	0,081
Our project coordinator @Grabovaclgor was presenting the #CANCERLESS project within the @CancerLeagues event jointly with @CbigScreen @equitycancerla1 @EUTOPIA_Screen @PrescripTec #Cancer #homeless #homelessness #poverty #healthcare #leavenoonebehind #EUCancerPlan #H2020 pic.twitter.com/UyRwvUAWUJ	601	48	0,08

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Our findings indicate that #patientnavigation is associated with a wide range of positive #health -related outcomes. We will pilot the Health Navigator Model, co-designed to improve #cancer #prevention among people experiencing #homelessness https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/10530789.2021.2021363 ... @EdelAldasoro	324	25	0,077
March 22 - June 22			
Interventions to improve cancer screening in homeless population pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30084381/ Follow us on Instagram! instagram.com/cancerless_eu/ #homelessness #health #EUcanbeatcancer #EUCancerPlan #H2020 pic.twitter.com/iOI8T1XTFH	198	19	9,60%
Our wonderful team is in #ICIC22 #ICIC2022!!! @Grabovaclgor @ChoniDM @SchifflerTobias @chcarmichael_ and Pania @_Proleptis cc @IFICInfo @GrabovacGroup @Polibienestar pic.twitter.com/n3FXXGIR1s	696	67	9,60%
Just starting our "blended" transnational meeting! Cambridge+online 🧑🧑🧑 Nice to see you all together! At last! 🙌 #Cambridge #h2020 #cancer #publichealth #leavingnoonebehind pic.twitter.com/qCYuSdArCP	1050	93	8,90%
Jun 22 - Sep 22			
ETHOS was developed through a review of existing definitions of #homelessness and the realities of homelessness which service providers are faced with on a daily basis https://www.feantsa.org/download/ethospaper20063618592914136463249.pdf ... #homeless #leavenoonebehind #EUcanbeatcancer #EUCancerPlan #H2020 @feantsa pic.twitter.com/LSuI54zVU6	107	9	8,4
Population-wide screening programmes have many challenges and barriers in engaging with the target population. Visit our	263	18	6,80%

<p>Instagram for knowing more! </p> <p>instagram.com/cancerless_eu/ #Cancer #homeless #poverty #healthcare #leavenoonebehind #EUcanbeatcancer #EUCancerPlan #H2020 pic.twitter.com/v1WdVn931L</p>			
<p>Creating low barrier means to meeting people where they are at was the foundation of developing an integrated plan to assist #women, #trans and #gender diverse individuals in Hamilton, Canada Know more: cancerless.eu/women's-trans-d... #healthdisparities #queer #women #womenshealth pic.twitter.com/x8T9XXnYwH</p>	357	24	6,70%
Sep 22 - Dec 22			
<p>Our #capacityBuilding consists of phases: needs assessment, formulation of strategies, implementation of actions, monitoring and evaluation, re-planning, and closely linked. +info: https://cancerless.eu/cancerless-capacity-building/ ... #Training #homeless #homelessness #EUcanbeatcancer #EUCancerPlan #H2020 pic.twitter.com/1QspmTPjvw</p>	100	13	13%
<p>#Madrid. A total of 3363 persons were registered as homeless in the Community of Madrid in 2019 cancerless.eu/project/spain-... Our Instagram: instagram.com/cancerless_eu/ #homeless #healthdisparities #healthinequalities #cancer #EUcanbeatcancer #EUCancerPlan #H2020 pic.twitter.com/xKYAGPm7Wg</p>	168	16	9,50%
<p>Did you know...? #BreastCancer is less susceptible to environmental exposures compared to other cancers in the list. Family history is key #BreastCancerAwarenessMonth #woman #homeless #homelessness #healthcare #leavenoonebehind #EUcanbeatcancer #EUCancerPlan #H2020 pic.twitter.com/KCmL7PRDAN</p>	213	17	8%
Jan 23 - Feb 23			

<p>Whist most people experiencing homelessness are men, roughly 20% – 30% are #women and #nonBinary individuals https://cancerless.eu/homelessness-and-women/ ... #Health #homeless #Cancer #leavenoonebehind #EUcanbeatcancer #EUCancerPlan #H2020 pic.twitter.com/jYpCs5eho7</p>	36	25	69,4%
<p>While it's an important step, it provides limited insight on #HealthInequalities: #Housing is a social determinant of health and should be included as indicator +Info at https://cancerless.eu/european-cancer-inequalities-registry/ ... #Health #homeless #Cancer #leavenoonebehind #EUcanbeatcancer #EUCancerPlan #H2020 pic.twitter.com/fZcsl4JpZh</p>	27	21	77,8%
Mar 23 - May 23			
<p>Today, we are sharing our project outcomes with Madrid regional officers in the fields of #socialServices and #PublicHealth #cancer #EUCancerPlan #homelessness pic.twitter.com/JkEt2oFC97</p>	43	21	48,8%
<p>Today, our coordinator, @Grabovaclgor, explains the why and the how of CANCERLESS in the #NavigatingHealth webinar cc @UniMelb @NavHealthIO #homelessness #cancer #healthnavigator #PublicHealth pic.twitter.com/ThQpcufobk</p>	57	16	28,1%
<p>Interventions with a longitudinal approach and a navigator who is non-clinical expert support the implementation of the patient/Health Navigator model among underserved communities https://cancerless.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/D2.1-Synthesis-Report_HNM-Homelessness-1.pdf ... #EWAC2023 #EUCancerPlan #MissionCancer #healthcare #homelessness #H2020 pic.twitter.com/Tz6rPbm53s</p>	676	16	2%
Jun 23 - Aug 23			
<p>Our new paper is fully open access, available at https://thelancet.com/journals/eclinm/article/PIIS2589-5370(23)00272-9/fulltext</p>	1740	48	8,6%

<p>Let us pay the way for a more inclusive society and effective cancer prevention strategies!</p> <p>#Cancer #homelessness #poverty #healthcare #leavenoonebehind #EUcanbeatcancer #EUCancerPlan #H2020</p>			
<p> @SchifflerTobias from the @MedUni_Wien sits down with Ben Burwood, Editor-in-Chief of eClinicalMedicine, to delve into the remarkable outcomes of the CANCERLESS project 🌞 📄</p> <p>#CANCERLESS #healthcare #cancerprevention #EUresearch #H2020</p>	610	16	6%
Sep 23 - Nov 23			
<p> @DiakonieAmber and @MedUni_Wien lead the Austrian pilot of CANCERLESS. Their Health Navigator model reinforces patient empowerment through social support, improving access to preventive services 🧑 📄</p> <p>#Cancer #homeless #homelessness #poverty #healthcare #EUCancerPlan #H2020</p>	1764	43	4,47%
<p>Did you know that...?</p> <p>Survival for #breastcancer patients has improved, thanks to advances in #earlydetection, new treatments and ongoing research</p> <p>#WorldBreastCancerDay #woman #poverty #homelessnessprevention #healthcare #leavenoonebehind #EUcanbeatcancer #EUCancerPlan</p>	1062	56	8,6%
<p> Yesterday, our colleague @IrfanMLone was ambassador of @CANCERLESS_EU at #EuropeanCancerSummit</p> <p>Let's do all we can to put Europe's focus on #health and #inclusion</p> <p>Great work Irfan!</p> <p>@EuropeanCancer @EU_Commission</p> <p>#EUCancerSummit #EUcanbeatcancer #H2020</p>	1145	54	7,8%

Dec 23 - Feb 24			
<p>Find out all the details of the #EuropeanCancerSummit 2023 and our colleague @IrfanMLone's contribution to the @CANCERLESS_EU project and to research, advocacy and policy on vital aspects of cancer prevention</p> <p>https://cancerless.eu/the-cancerless-project-at-the-european-cancer-summit/</p> <p>#EUCancerPlan @EuropeanCancer @FEANTSA</p>	632	31	11,6%
<p>🌟 @EPHA_EU has shared a new @FEANTSA article on #homelessness and #cancer, as part of its health equity thematic group. The article highlights the #CANCERLESS project, bringing its focus to a wider audience</p> <p>https://epha.org/bridging-the-gap-between-the-dual-burden-of-homelessness-and-cancer-across-europe/ ...</p> <p>#EUCancerPlan #LeaveNoOneBehind</p>	478	20	4,2%
<p>The @CANCERLESS_EU consortium meets again. This time in Valencia!</p> <p>Thanks for the organisation to @Polibienestar 🍷🍷🍷🍷</p> <p>#EUCancerPlan #LeaveNoOneBehind #homeless #Health #HE #HealthCare pic.twitter.com/HCJxsRbSFO</p>	1088	55	5,1%
Mar 24 - May 24			
<p>CANCERLESS @CANCERLESS_EU</p> <p>Join the event "Improving Access to Cancer Screening and Prevention among People Experiencing Homelessness"</p> <p>March 19, 16:00-18:00 CET, at the European Parliament</p> <p>Organized by @FEANTSA and MEP @Kympouropoulos</p> <p>https://tinyurl.com/2b5qhrag</p>	1324	52	3,9%
<p>Our colleague @Juliajulaas presented yesterday the @CANCERLESS_EU project at the 24th International Conference on Integrated Care, organised by our partner @IFICInfo 🍷🍷</p>	258	14	5,4%

<p>#ICIC24 #EUCancerPlan #Health #HealthCare #Research https://twitter.com/Juliajulaas/status/1782423597396472271 ...</p>			
<p>News from the CANCERLESS!</p> <p>We are at the final project meeting in Vienna, reflecting on our achievements and discussing strategies to sustain our impact. We thank our team for their dedication and look forward to the next chapter of our journey.</p> <p>#EUCancerPlan #homeless #Health pic.twitter.com/Dw7NZMpaFS</p>	933	79	8,5%

These engagement rates – considering as well the general engagement rate of 2,5% - show an excellent performance, which means that, regardless of the number of followers – which are limited by both, the target groups but also the type of account (A project, nothing personal, etc.) – these followers are really interested and engaged with the content.

4.9. Scientific dissemination

Congresses and conferences

The CANCERLESS project has actively participated in numerous congresses and conferences, strategically disseminating its findings and interacting with various stakeholders across Europe and beyond on cancer prevention and screening among homeless populations. Through workshops, poster presentations and symposia, the project has highlighted its commitment to promoting health equity and access to care for vulnerable communities, fostering collaborative action and sharing knowledge with key stakeholders.

Through presentations at international events such as the European Cancer Summit and the International Urban Health Conference, CANCERLESS has underlined its dedication to promoting evidence-based solutions to improve cancer care among PEH. With each participation, the project reinforces its role as a trigger for change, driving conversations and initiatives aimed at addressing health care challenges and promoting health equity for all. Through its ongoing participation in conferences and forums, CANCERLESS

continues to advance its mission to combat cancer among PEH and contribute to the broader goal of improving health outcomes for marginalised communities across Europe (please see Table 5).

Table 8 - CANCERLESS Congresses and Conferences

Partner	Date	Title	Place	Reference or details
IFIC	25/05/2021	Workshop: Implementing the Health Navigator Model among the Homeless Population in Europe – the CANCERLESS Project	Online	ICIC 2021 Virtual Conference. CANCERLESS Project presented by Igor Grbaovac and Alejandro Gil-Salmeron, moderated by Edelweiss Aldasoro
IFIC	25/05/2022	Beyond CANCERLESS: Building up strategies to guarantee the scalability and transferability of the Health Navigator Model to real-life settings across Europe ⁵	Face-to-face	ICIC 2022 Conference Odense, Denmark. CANCERLESS Project presented by Igor Grabovac, Tobias Schiffler, Alejandro Gil-Salmeron, Christina Carmichael, Pania Karnaki and Ascensión Doñate
FEANTSA	16-17/11/2022	Poster presentation ⁶	Brussels	At the European Cancer Summit and online
SERMAS	22/10/2022	Poster presented about CANCERLESS Pilot in Madrid⁷	Face-to-face	95th Biannual Conference of the European General Practice Research Network (EGPRN). Project presented by: Gómez Trenado R., Barrio Cortes J., Gil Salmerón A., Gómez Gascón T., Grabovac I., Moreno Moreno M., Rico Varadé M., Cancerles Collaborative Group
KVC	24/10/2022-27/10/2022	Health communication and recruitment of hard-to-	Valencia, Spain	Valina, B.*, Dominguez, L., Costa, B & Ferrando, M. (2022). Health communication and recruitment of hard-to-reach and highly marginalized populations. International Conference of

⁵ <https://integratedcarefoundation.org/events/icic22-22nd-international-conference-on-integrated-care>

⁶ <https://twitter.com/FEANTSA/status/1592821350858489856/photo/1>

⁷ <https://meeting.egprn.org/>

		reach and highly marginalized populations ⁸		Urban Health (ICUH 22). October 24th-27th. Valencia (Spain)
MUW/IFIC	09/11/2022 – 12/11/2022	Barriers and facilitators to healthcare access for experiencing homelessness people in four European countries	Berlin, Germany	Schiffler, T., Carmichael, C., Lehner, L., Gil-Salmeron, A., Kouvari, M., Karnaki, P., Grabovac, I. (2022) Barriers and facilitators to healthcare access for experiencing homelessness people in four European countries. European Journal of Public Health, Volume 32, Issue Supplement_3, October 2022, ckac129.068, https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckac129.068
MUW/IFIC	09/11/2022 – 12/11/2022	Barriers to access cancer prevention services for the homeless population in four European countries	Berlin, Germany	Schiffler, T., Carmichael, C., Gil-Salmeron, A., Kouvari, M., Karnaki, P., Grabovac, I. (2022) Barriers to access cancer prevention services for the homeless population in four European countries. European Journal of Public Health, Volume 32, Issue Supplement_3, October 2022, ckac129.069, https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckac129.069
MUW/IFIC	09/11/2022 – 12/11/2022	Application of the patient navigation model with people experiencing homelessness: a scoping review	Berlin, Germany	Grabovac, I., Carmichael, C., Smith, L., Aldasoro, E., Gil-Salmeron, A., Alhambra-Borras, T., Donate-Martinez, A., Seiler-Ramadas, R. (2022) Application of the patient navigation model with people experiencing homelessness: a scoping review. European Journal of Public Health, Volume 32, Issue Supplement_3, October 2022, ckac129.422, https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/ckac129.422

⁸ https://isuhconference2022.onsitevents.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/ICUH-2022-Oral-Program_09-30-2022.pdf

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MUW	09/05/2023	Health and Homelessness - what is the role of the homelessness sector?	Vienna (Austria)	International workshop on best practices for healthcare for PEH organized by a local Austrian NGO "Neunerhaus" with participation from FEANTSA
IFIC	12/05/2023	XIV CONGRESO ESTATAL DE TRABAJO SOCIAL Y SALUD	A Coruña (Spain)	IFIC presented the results of WP2
SERMAS	12/05/2023	XIV Spanish State Congress of Social Work and Health (AETSYS) - Innovating and expanding the capabilities of the health system	A Coruña (Spain)	FIIBAP (SERMAS) presented the preliminary results regarding the Social Determinants of Health and the Barriers to Primary Care Access detected in Madrid
FEANTSA	25/05/2022	World Congress of Psycho-oncology	Milan (Italy)	World Congress of Psycho-oncology, Milan. CANCERLESS Project presented FEANTSA
IFIC	05/06/2023	EHMA 2023 - Health management: sustainable solutions for complex systems	Rome (Italy)	IFIC presented the results of WP2
SERMAS	23/06/2023	IFSW EUROPEAN CONFERENCE 2023.	Prague (Czech Republic)	Madrid presents the first results of barriers to access to the health system in Madrid
FEANTSA	10/07/2023	17th European Research Conference on Homelessness		Promotion of CANCERLESS in the context of the upcoming 17th European Research Conference on Homelessness
FEANTSA	20-21/09/23	World Cancer Series	Brussels	World Cancer Series, Brussels. FEANTSA represented the CANCERLESS project.
FEANTSA	10/10/2023	Mental Health Conference	Brussels	Mental Health Conference, Brussels. FEANTSA represented the CANCERLESS project.
IFIC	25/10/2023	HMI Conference Dublin	Dublin	IFIC exhibited at the health management conference in Dublin showcasing the

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				work involved in CANCERLESS and other projects
IFIC	02/11/2023	MTU Symposium Ireland	MTU Kerry, Ireland	MTU and IFIC co-hosted a symposium with past participants of their joint course, there were CANCERLESS leaflets present to show the work that IFIC is involved in.
FEANTSA	08/11/2023	Continenence Health Summit	Brussels	Continenence Health Summit, Brussels. FEANTSA represented the CANCERLESS project.
FEANTSA	09/11/2023	European Economic and Social Committee	Brussels	European Economic and Social Committee, Brussels. FEANTSA represented the CANCERLESS project.
FEANTSA	15-16/11/23	European Cancer Summit	Brussels	European Cancer Summit, Brussels. CANCERLESS Project presented FEANTSA
FEANTSA	17/11/2023	Interact Europe	Brussels	Interact Europe, Brussels. FEANTSA represented the CANCERLESS project.
FEANTSA	21/11/2023	Pancreatic Cancer Europe: Physical exercise and cancer	Online	Pancreatic Cancer Europe. CANCERLESS Project presented FEANTSA
FEANTSA	19/11/2024 - 24/11/24	World Anti-microbial Resistance (AMR) Week	Online	World Anti-microbial Resistance (AMR) Week. FEANTSA represented the CANCERLESS project.
FEANTSA	29/11/2023	A comprehensive approach to Mental Health- EU Parliament	Brussels	A comprehensive approach to Mental Health- EU Parliament, Brussels. FEANTSA represented the CANCERLESS project.
FEANTSA	29/11/2023	Men & cancer: Manifesto release ECO at EU parliament	Brussels	Men & cancer, Brussels. FEANTSA represented the CANCERLESS project.
FEANTSA	05/12/2023	European Cancer Forum	Brussels	European Cancer Forum, Brussels. FEANTSA represented the CANCERLESS project.

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FEANTSA	06/12/2023	Racism, discrimination, and health: a human rights-based approach-EPHA	Brussels	Racism, discrimination, and health, Brussels. FEANTSA represented the CANCERLESS project.
FEANTSA	08/12/2023	Universal access & Affordable medicine Forum: EPHA	Brussels	Universal access & Affordable medicine Forum: EPHA, Brussels. FEANTSA represented the CANCERLESS project.
FEANTSA	11/12/2023	Accelerating Cancer Care in Europe	Brussels	Accelerating Cancer Care in Europe, Brussels. CANCERLESS Project presented FEANTSA
ARU	18/01/2024	Pathway Masterclass	Online	Online Masterclass titled "Introducing the CANCERLESS project and the Health Navigator Model"
ARU	22/01/2024	"Nursing and Allied Health Professionals Virtual Event on equality, diversity and inclusion"	Online	Presentation titled "Introducing the CANCERLESS project and the Health Navigator Model"
FEANTSA	22/01/2024	OECD High Policy meeting in Paris on People centered Health Innovation	Paris (France)	FEANTSA participation and representation of CANCERLESS at this High-Level Global Stakeholder Conference, representing CANCERLESS project and ensuring Homeless population with cancer are not left behind in policy inclusion.
FEANTSA	25/01/2024	Turning the tide: Increasing participation in cervical cancer screening to save women's lives- High Level EU parliament Event	Brussels	FEANTSA participation and representation of CANCERLESS at this High Level European Parliamentary Conference to advocate for participation and inclusion of women facing homelessness in Cervical.
FEANTSA	31/01/2024	EU Commission-Europe's Beatings Cancer Plan Update	Brussels	EU Commission-Europe's Beatings Cancer Plan Update, Brussels. CANCERLESS Project presented FEANTSA

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FEANTSA	05-06/03/24	World EPA Congress	Amsterdam	World EPA Congress, Amsterdam. FEANTSA represented the CANCERLESS project.
FEANTSA	19/03/2024	Stakeholder Meeting on Improving Access to Cancer Screening & Prevention among People Experiencing Homelessness in Europe: The CANCERLESS Project	Brussels	A stakeholder meeting for the CANCERLESS project took place on March 19, 2024, at the European Parliament in Brussels. Hosted by Mr. Stelios Kypouropoulos (MEP, Greece), the gathering aimed to improve cancer screening and prevention access for homeless individuals across Europe. Organised by FEANTSA. Involvement of project partners.
FEANTSA	09/04/2024	Fighting Lung Cancer as Equals- a year in	Brussels	FEANTSA will participate in High-level policy event on lung cancer Representing CANCERLESS. We will emphasise on improved and fair screening and prevention of lung cancer among PEH, which is one of the leading cancers and cause of mortality in this group.
FEANTSA	15-16/04/24	Economist Impat-Cell & Gene Therapy Summit	Brussels	FEANTSA will participate in High-level 2-Day congress on Innovation in personalised medicine. We will discuss about the equity, inclusion, universal health coverage for PEH and the role of industry to contribute to paradigm shift for fair inclusion in innovation.
MUW	18/04/2023	#Navigating Health Globally: Point of Navigation: Equity of Access & Outcomes	Online	International Webinar on patient navigation to improve equity in access to cancer prevention organised by University of Melbourne (Australia)
ARU	22/04/2024	ICIC24 Conference	Belfast	Presenting CANCERLESS at the ICIC24 Conference in Belfast
IFIC	22/04/2024	ICIC24 Conference	Belfast	Event organisation and presentation of CANCERLESS at the ICIC24 Belfast Conference

FEANTSA	17-18/05/2024	FEANTSA Forum 2024	Vienna	The FEANTSA Forum is our annual flagship event to discuss the latest practices, strategies, research, services, and policies in the fight against homelessness. Presentation of the CANCERLESS project.
PRAKSIS	28/05/2024	"Social Work in the Streets of Thessaloniki, Methodology and Experiences"	Greece, Thessaloniki	PRAKSIS participated in the A' Thematic Session Approach and support of homeless population on the topic Homelessness and practices of approach and support: data, context, interventions. In this context, the Cancerless project and the Health Navigator model were presented.

Scientific articles

Scientific articles play a key role in the dissemination of research results, as they provide a platform for specialists to share ideas, methodologies, and outcomes with their colleagues and the wider academic community. Furthermore, these articles provide a platform for specialists to share their expertise and contribute to the advancement of knowledge in their field.

The CANCERLESS project has published a series of articles that contribute to the body of knowledge on cancer prevention and access to healthcare for homeless populations in Europe. These articles delve into various aspects of the project, exploring topics such as the application of the navigation model with PEH, the co-design of the Health Navigator Model for Austria, and the identification of current barriers in healthcare provision for homeless populations in relation to cancer prevention.

In addition to exploring these topics, the articles also discuss strategies to ensure scalability and transferability of the Health Navigator model across Europe. They also examine ethical considerations and lessons learned from the CANCERLESS project.

Through rigorous qualitative studies, exploratory research, and ethical analysis, these articles shed light on the complexities and challenges inherent in providing equitable cancer prevention services to homeless populations. The CANCERLESS project aims to inform policy and practice, ultimately improving health outcomes for vulnerable communities across Europe. Please see below the publications:

- Carmichael, C., Smith, L., Aldasoro, E., Gil Salmerón, A., Alhambra-Borrás, T., Doñate-Martínez, A., ... & Grabovac, I. (2022). Exploring the application of the navigation model with people experiencing homelessness: a scoping review. *Journal of Social Distress and Homelessness*, 1-15. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/10530789.2021.2021363>

This comprehensive review, accessed 2,779 times and cited by CrossRef three times to date, has earned an Altmetric score of 15, indicating its impact on several online platforms. The results underscore the potential of Patient Navigation (PN) to mitigate health care disparities among underserved populations, particularly the homeless. While highlighting consistent associations between PN and improved health-related outcomes, the review emphasises the need for more research to explore the feasibility and effectiveness of PN in diverse geographic contexts outside the US. By addressing implementation barriers and leveraging facilitators, PN interventions can improve access to health services and contribute to improved health outcomes for underserved populations worldwide.

- Jeleff, M., Markovic, L., Lehner, L., Schiffler, T., & Grabovac, I. (2022). Anwendung der Patientennavigation bei obdachlosen Menschen: ein Scoping Review (CANCERLESS). *Das Gesundheitswesen*, 84(08/09). <https://www.thieme-connect.com/products/ejournals/html/10.1055/s-0042-1751177>

This study, presented as a scoping review, analyses the application of the patient navigation model (PNM) in homeless and other underserved populations. The results, published in the *Journal of Social Distress and Homelessness*, show that PNM is associated with improvements in a variety of health outcomes. Despite variability in implementation, consistent patterns in barriers and facilitators are identified.

- Schiffler, T., Jeleff, M., Lehner, L., Markovic, L., & Grabovac, I. (2022). Co-Design des Health Navigator Modells für Österreich: das CANCERLESS Projekt. Das Gesundheitswesen, 84(08/09). <https://www.thieme-connect.com/products/ejournals/html/10.1055/s-0042-1751149>

This article, presented as a qualitative study, explores the development of the Health Navigator model (HNM) as part of the CANCERLESS project, targeting homeless and precariously housed people in Europe. A focus group discussion was conducted using DeGroff's conceptual framework to identify and elaborate the ten main components of the HNM. The participants, coming from a variety of professional backgrounds related to homelessness care, collaborated in defining the overall concept of HNM, the profile of Health Navigators and evaluation measures. The findings highlight the importance of a person- and community-centred approach, addressing both cancer prevention and general barriers to accessing care among this vulnerable population. The focus group discussion underlined the potential of HNM to identify and address health and social needs in at-risk groups early, as well as to empower patients and improve health competence.

- Schiffler, T., Lehner, L., Jeleff, M., Markovic, L., & Grabovac, I. (2022). Obdachlosigkeit und Krebsvorsorge: Aktuelle Barrieren in der Gesundheitsversorgung (CANCERLESS). Das Gesundheitswesen, 84(08/09). <https://www.thieme-connect.com/products/ejournals/html/10.1055/s-0042-1751148>

The CANCERLESS (EU-Horizon 2020) project aims to develop the Health Navigator Model (HNM) to improve access to cancer prevention for PEH in Europe. To adapt this model to the Austrian health system, 19 semi-structured interviews were conducted with PEH and health sector experts between August and October 2021. The results identified five key themes: health needs, barriers and facilitators of access to care, experiences with cancer, and public health intervention strategies. They highlighted the need to offer expert cancer prevention in settings familiar to PEH and with personalised services. These findings will guide the implementation of the HNM.

This publication is a peer-reviewed academic article and is intended for a diverse audience including clinicians and medical students.

- Gil-salmerón, A., Grabovac, I., Karnaki, P., Doñate-Martinez, A., Carmichael, C., & Schiffler, T. (2022). *Beyond CANCERLESS: Building up strategies to guarantee the scalability and transferability of the Health Navigator Model to real-life settings across Europe*. (S3). 22(S3), Article S3. <https://doi.org/10.5334/ijic.ICIC22438>

The CANCERLESS project aims to reduce health inequalities among the homeless population in Europe through the Health Navigator Model (HNM), a model that includes health promotion, counselling and support in navigating the healthcare system. Conducted in Austria, Greece, Spain and the UK, the exploratory qualitative study identified five key themes: health needs, factors hindering and facilitating access to care, experiences with cancer, and strategies for public health interventions. The results underline the importance of providing cancer prevention in familiar settings and with a proactive approach tailored to individual needs. The article is aimed at health and social care professionals, researchers, public authorities and third sector organisations.

The International Journal of Integrated Care (IJIC) is a leading academic journal that focuses on integrated health and social care, publishing research, case studies and articles on the implementation and impact of integrated care models around the world. Its scope covers topics such as models and approaches to integrated care, coordination between health and social services, programme and policy evaluations, and innovations in integrated health service delivery. With an audience that includes researchers, health professionals, policy makers and students, IJIC plays a key role in promoting the exchange of knowledge and best practices in the field of integrated care, thus contributing to improving the quality and efficiency of health care services.

- Schiffler, T., Carmichael, C., Smith, L., Doñate-Martínez, A., Alhambra-Borrás, T., Varadé, M. R., Cortes, J. B., Kouvari, M., Karnaki, P., Moudatsou, M., Tabaki, I., Gil-Salmeron, A., & Grabovac, I. (2023). Access to cancer preventive care and program considerations for people experiencing homelessness across four

European countries: An exploratory qualitative study. *EClinicalMedicine*, 62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2023.102095>

Access to cancer preventive care and programme considerations for people experiencing homelessness in four European countries were explored in a qualitative study published in *EClinicalMedicine*. Those experiencing homelessness have a higher prevalence of adverse health outcomes and premature mortality compared to the non-homeless population, including a heavier burden of cancer and cancer-specific morbidity and mortality. These outcomes may be a consequence of significant barriers to accessing primary and secondary prevention and community health services. This study sought to better understand the health needs and barriers to accessing cancer preventive care for PEH in four European countries, as well as the considerations needed to develop cancer prevention interventions for this population.

- Carmichael, C., Schiffler, T., Smith, L., Moudatsou, M., Tabaki, I., Doñate-Martínez, A., Alhambra-Borrás, T., Kouvari, M., Karnaki, P., Gil-Salmeron, A., & Grabovac, I. (2023). Barriers and facilitators to health care access for people experiencing homelessness in four European countries: An exploratory qualitative study. *International Journal for Equity in Health*, 22(1), 206. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12939-023-02011-4>

The exploratory qualitative study was published in the *International Journal for Equity in Health*. The study examines the specific health needs of PEH and the barriers and facilitators associated with their timely and equitable access to health services in the European context. Sixty-nine semi-structured interviews were conducted with PEH, health professionals and social work practitioners in Austria, Greece, Spain and the UK, and the results were organised into three main themes: the health care needs of PEH, barriers and facilitators to accessing health care. The results highlighted the need for personalised approaches and the involvement of trusted professionals in the provision of care as key strategies to overcome existing barriers.

- Jeleff, M., Haider, S., Schiffler, T., Gil-Salmerón, A., Yang, L., Schuch, F. B., & Grabovac, I. (2024). Cancer risk factors and access to cancer prevention services

for people experiencing homelessness. *The Lancet Public Health*, 9(2), e128-e146. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667\(23\)00298-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667(23)00298-0)

The article "Cancer risk factors and access to cancer prevention services for people experiencing homelessness" published in *The Lancet Public Health* addresses the importance of understanding cancer risk factors and barriers to accessing prevention services among PEH. Through an analysis of 40 studies, factors at the individual, interpersonal, systemic and policy levels that influence access to these services were identified. Findings highlight the need for interventions that facilitate access to cancer prevention through social support and navigation programmes, as well as training of health workers to create trusting environments that foster continuity of care. They highlight a high prevalence of cancer risk factors, such as tobacco use, among PEH, underscoring the importance of addressing these health disparities in a comprehensive and tailored manner for this vulnerable population.

- Coronado-Vázquez, M., Trenado, R., Benito-Sánchez, B., Barrio Cortes, J., Gil Salmerón, A., Amengual-Pliego, M., & Grabovac, I. (2024). Cancer prevention in people experiencing homelessness: Ethical considerations and experiences from the CANCERLESS project. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2024.1371505>

The article "Cancer prevention in people experiencing homelessness: ethical considerations and experiences from the CANCERLESS project", published in *Frontiers in Public Health*, addresses the increasing incidence of cancer in Europe and its impact on PEH, who face difficulties in accessing prevention programmes. The CANCERLESS project seeks to implement the Health Navigator model to promote cancer prevention and early detection. Ethical aspects are discussed according to the ethics of public health and care, highlighting the importance of social justice and equity in access to health systems. With 242 total views and 137 downloads, the study highlights the need to incorporate the preferences and values of affected people into decisions about cancer prevention.

Position paper

In the case of CANCERLESS, this element represents a crucial component in advocating for concrete policies and actions to address disparities in access to health care for PEH. These papers, produced in collaboration with relevant organisations such as FEANTSA, reflect the official position of the CANCERLESS consortium on specific issues related to the health and well-being of people experiencing homelessness (PEH) in Europe. Through these position papers, the project aims to influence policies and decisions at the European level, advocating for significant changes that promote equity in access to health care and cancer prevention for this vulnerable population.

- FEANTSA - 16/02/2022: FEANTSA and the CANCERLESS consortium call on the European Commission to include 'housing situation' as one of the inequality dimensions of the EU Cancer Registry. Direct communication with DG SANTE. English.
Available at <https://twitter.com/FEANTSA/status/1493905314948730882> and <https://cancerless.eu/housing-social-health/>

EU-funded Projects and stakeholders Networking

During the development of the project, synergies have been established and collaboration has taken place with more than 11 EU-funded projects, including CBIG-SCREEN, Equity cancer LA, PRESCRIP TEC, CHILI, EU-TOPIA east, EMOTIONAL CITIES, RECETAS, HEART, ENLIGHTENme, URBANOME and WELLBASED. The project has participated in various networking activities with stakeholders, including events organised by the European Cancer League and the Urban Health Cluster. These activities have also involved meetings with organisations such as Access Surgery, Clinical Psychologist, neunerhaus Peer Campus, and CRUK Cambridge Institute, among others. Through these collaborations, we have discussed potential partnerships, shared information, and explored opportunities for the future development of the project. Table 6 below, presents the list of these activities.

The CANCERLESS Project has been funded by the European Commission's Programme Horizon 2020 under the Grant Agreement 965351

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Table 9 - EU-funded and stakeholders Networking

PARTNER	Date	Title	Details
PROJECT	30/05/2022	Meet and greet (European Cancer League)	<p>Event organised by the European Partnership Against Cancer to promote key initiatives and recommendations in the fight against cancer at European and national level.</p>
PROJECT	27-28/10/2022	Urban Health Cluster	<p>The Urban Health Cluster 2022 aims to enhance and protect the health and well-being of all citizens, making it the foremost European initiative committed to inclusivity and equity in health.</p>
ARU	01/06/2023	Meeting with Access Surgery	<p>Meeting with the Access Surgery (provides health care for PEH) to receive more information about available Cancer support for the Homeless.02/08/2023.</p>
ARU	07/06/2023	Meeting with Clinical Psychologist	<p>Clinical Psychologist is involved in the overall and palliative care of PEH people in Cambridgeshire. She is based in the Access Surgery (surgery that provides care for PEH in Cambridge).</p>
ARU	07/06/2023	Homelessness, Health and Palliative Care:	<p>These are monthly meetings that CANCERLESS team in the UK is attending. These meetings cover issues around</p>

		Cambridge Community of Practice.	Homelessness, Health and Palliative Care of PEH. There is also a discussion on how to support PEH
MUW	07/06/2023	Meeting with members of neunerhaus Peer Campus	Meeting with peers to discuss a) what can be done to maintain the clients' motivation to participate; b) how can CANCERLESS be sustainable and continue to have an impact after the end of the Project
FEANTSA	09/06/2023	INTERACT & Cancerless project collaboration.	FEANTSA met with the European Cancer Organisation to discuss potential synergies between the CANCERLESS & INTERACT (ECO) projects, including the finalisation of the video recorded at the ECO Cancer Summit 2022.
MUW	20/06/2023	Meeting with members of neunerhaus Peer Campus	Meeting with peers to discuss a) what can be done to maintain the clients' motivation to participate; b) how can CANCERLESS be sustainable and continue to have an impact after the end of the Project,
IFIC	02/08/2023	Meeting with Social Work Department MútuaTerrasa (Catalonia).	Meeting with the department director and 4 social workers because they are applying for local funding for the adoption of the CANCERLESS model.
MUW	22/11/2023	Meeting with members of neunerhaus Peer Campus.	Meeting with peers to discuss how CANCERLESS can be made sustainable in Vienna
ARU		Meeting with Cambridge Access Surgery	Several meetings with GPs at the Access Surgery regarding Cancerless project, discussions about extending the HNM activities beyond the Cancerless project

ARU		Meeting with Cambridge Access Surgery	Several meetings with GPs at the Access Surgery regarding Cancerless project, discussions about extending the HNM activities beyond the Cancerless project
ARU		Meeting with CRUK Cambridge Institute	Several strategy meetings with CRUK Cambridge Institute to discuss workshop delivery and potential future funding

Workshops and webinars

Over the past 36 months, the CANCERLESS project has participated in a series of workshops and webinars focused on raising cancer awareness and promoting prevention among PEH.

These workshops and webinars have provided an invaluable opportunity for the CANCERLESS project to further disseminate its objectives and activities, as well as to share knowledge with various stakeholders. Participation in events focused on cancer awareness has facilitated the identification of specific needs of PEH in terms of preventive health, contributing to the adaptation and continuous improvement of the project's interventions. Moreover, representation at international webinars has allowed the CANCERLESS project to establish collaborations and synergies with other projects and organisations at European and international level, thus strengthening its impact and outreach in the fight against cancer among PEH. Table 7 below, presents a list of workshops and webinars.

Table 10 - Workshops and webinars

PARTNER	Date	Title	Place	Reference or details
IFIC	02/12/2022	CANCERLESS Webinar Hosted by IFIC	International	CANCERLESS Consortium presented an overview of the project and pilots to 33 attendees.

ARU	10/01/2023	1st Big C cancer awareness workshop about men's health	Purfleet - King's Lynn	Prostate cancer, 14 PEH attended (both men and women)
ARU	14/02/2023	2nd Big C cancer awareness workshop about women's health	Purfleet - King's Lynn	Cervical cancer, 11 PEH attended (both men and women)
MUW	22/02/2023	CANCERLESS-Workshop for people experiencing homelessness	Vienna (Austria)	Dissemination of the HNM intervention in a Caritas day-care centre
IFIC	26/03/2023	EU Navigate Webinar by ECO	Online	FEANTSA participated in a high-level global stakeholder webinar organized by ECO on European Union Navigate, with the goal of sharing best practices and knowledge in patient navigation in cancer care. We shared insights and learnings from our Cancerless project with these stakeholders.
ARU	17/04/2023	Workshop on exercise and nutrition by MITT FIT	Cambridge	Second workshop on exercise and nutrition in Jimmy's 451. (2 PEH attended)
ARU	25/04/2023	3rd Big C cancer awareness workshop about diet and nutrition	Purfleet - King's Lynn	3rd workshop on diet and nutrition presented by Big C Cancer Charity. (11 PEH attended).
MUW	26/04/2023	Health and Cancer Prevention Workshop at CARITAS Daycentre for PEH	Vienna (Austria)	MUW team delivered a half-day workshop on health promotion and cancer prevention at the CARITAS

				daycentre for people experiencing homelessness. In addition to providing comprehensive health education on nutrition, physical activity, safer sex practices, and vaccination, we also conducted blood pressure and blood sugar level screenings, as well as offered overall health counselling.
ARU	15/05/2023	Workshop on Wellbeing in Jimmys' 451	Cambridge	Workshop on Wellbeing in Jimmy's 451 delivered by Julia Gawronska (1 PEH attended)
MUW	19/07/2023	CANCERLESS workshop	Vienna, Austria	The workshop was conducted at the Caritas day centre for people experiencing homelessness (information on e.g. cancer preventive measures, CANCERLESS programme)
IFIC	13/09/2023	Inclusion Health Special Interest Group (SIG)	Online	Inclusion Health Webinar hosted by IFIC, speakers include Alejandro presenting on CANCERLESS
MUW	26/03/2024	Patient Navigation: The Path Towards Reduced Cancer Inequalities in Europe?	Online	Igor Grabovac, present the CANCERLESS project. Patient navigation for optimal access to cancer treatment and information –

				the My Cancer Navigator service
MUW	26/03/2024	EU Navigate Webinar by ECO	Online	Igor Grabovac participated in a high-level Global stakeholder webinar organised by ECO on EU Navigate, with the focus to share best practices and knowledge in patient navigation in cancer care. We represented Cancerless and the insights and learnings from the project with these stakeholders;
ARU	03/04/2023	Workshop on exercise and nutrition by MITT FIT	Cambridge	First workshop on exercise and nutrition in Jimmy's 451 (1 PEH attended)

4.10. Media appearances

The CANCERLESS project has generated a great deal of interest and repercussion in the media and dissemination platforms both nationally and internationally. Through a variety of articles, interviews and coverage, the importance of addressing cancer among PEH has been highlighted, as well as the innovative initiatives the project is implementing to prevent and detect cancer among this vulnerable group. From publications in leading media outlets to mentions on social media and academic platforms, the CANCERLESS project has managed to capture the attention of diverse audiences and promote greater awareness of the need for equity in access to health care and cancer prevention for all people, regardless of their housing situation. The relevant links are the followings:

- <https://quo.eldiario.es/salud/q2106172360/cancer-homeless-cancerless-igor-gravovac/>

- <https://www.elmostrador.cl/agenda-pais/2022/12/04/las-personas-sin-hogar-viven-menos-que-el-resto-de-la-poblacion/>
- <https://phys.org/news/2022-12-homelessness-stark-impact-health-clearer.html>
- <https://theconversation.com/las-personas-sin-hogar-viven-menos-que-el-resto-de-la-poblacion-195032#:~:text=Las%20personas%20sin%20hogar%20ven,o%20cronifican%20as%20ya%20existentes>
- <https://theconversation.com/as-homelessness-grows-its-stark-impact-on-health-is-becoming-clearer-across-europe-195989>
- <https://epha.org/bridging-the-gap-between-the-dual-burden-of-homelessness-and-c>
- https://www.consalud.es/saludigital/tecnologia-sanitaria/equipo-upv-proyecto-europeo-prevenir-cancer-personas-sin-hogar_142461_102.html
- https://twitter.com/BDSLab_UPV/status/1778070795870167484
- <https://epha.org/epha-newsletter-making-headway-on-health-equity/>
- <https://www.cam.ac.uk/stories/close-the-cancer-care-gap>
- <https://epha.org/bridging-the-gap-between-the-dual-burden-of-homelessness-and-cancer-across-europe/>
- <https://medriva.com/cancer/addressing-the-higher-risk-of-cancer-among-the-homeless-a-call-for-tailored-prevention-measures/>
- https://www.apuntmedia.es/noticies/societat/upv-participa-una-investigacio-europea-previndre-cancer-persones-llar_1_1697063.html
- https://cadenaser.com/comunitat-valenciana/2024/04/07/un-equipo-de-la-universitat-politecnica-de-valencia-participa-en-un-proyecto-europeo-para-prevenir-el-cancer-en-personas-sin-hogar-radio-valencia/?rel=buscador_noticias
- <https://www.buzzsprout.com/1845316/13468864>
- <https://www.ittralee.ie/en/>
- https://hadea.ec.europa.eu/news/discover-cancerless-eu-funded-project-aimed-serving-people-experiencing-homelessness-2024-02-02_en
- <https://www.researchgate.net/lab/Grabovac-Group-Igor-Grabovac>

- <https://oncologynews.com.au/latest-news/cancer-among-people-experiencing-homelessness-research-into-current-situation-forms-basis-for-prevention-program/>

The numerous media appearances related to the CANCERLESS project have provided a significant platform to spread its message and raise awareness of the importance of addressing cancer among PEH. With an estimated combined reach of 30-50 million readers, these news stories have helped to highlight the impact of the project and highlight the urgent need for cancer prevention programmes tailored to this vulnerable population. In addition to the broad quantitative visibility, the interviews and articles provide a qualitative platform to delve deeper into the challenges and solutions associated with cancer prevention in homeless communities, generating discussion and promoting action on public health and healthcare equity.

4.11. Publications on the partners' website

The publications on the CANCERLESS project partners' websites provide a detailed overview of the project's activities and achievements across various domains. From the presentation of specific initiatives to interviews with the project coordinator, these pages provide detailed information on the project's objectives and results. In addition, they highlight the partners' active participation in events and meetings related to cancer prevention among PEH, as well as promoting awareness and understanding of the challenges faced by this population. These publications not only enhance the visibility of the project, but also underline the partners' commitment to improving the health and well-being of PEHs in Europe.

Some partners have featured the project on their respective websites as follows:

- <https://www.comunidad.madrid/servicios/asuntos-sociales/proyecto-cancerless>: Cancerless is a project that is promoted by the Community of Madrid, which seeks to promote cancer prevention and early detection in experiencing homelessness people in Madrid.

- <https://www.polibienestar.org/portfolio/cancerless/>: This page shows the activities and initiatives of the Cancerless project, which is part of the POLIBIENESTAR research group.
- <https://kveloce.com/project/cancerless-cancer-prevention-and-early-detection-among-the-homeless-population-in-europe-co-adapting-and-implementing-the-health-navigator-model/>: This page provides information on the Cancerless project
- <https://kveloce.com/cancerless-igor-grabovac/>: This page reflects an interview to Igor Grabovac, the project coordinator of the Cancerless project, in Spanish
- <https://kveloce.com/en/cancerless-igor-grabovac/>: This page reflects an interview to Igor Grabovac, the project coordinator of the Cancerless project, English version.
- <https://www.feantsa.org/en/project/2022/02/03/the-cancerless-project?bcParent=418>: This page provides information on the Cancerless project, which is a European Union-funded project that seeks to improve cancer prevention and early detection among experiencing homelessness people in Europe.
- https://integratedcarefoundation.org/research_projects/cancerless: Information about the CANCERLESS project
- <https://praksis.gr/cancerless/>: Information about the CANCERLESS project
- <https://www.prolepsis.gr/gr/programs/cancerless>: Information about the CANCERLESS project
- <https://www.prolepsis.gr/gr/news/pagkosmia-imerakata-tou-karkinou-2022-to-europaiko-programma-cancerless>: This page provides information on the Cancerless project, which is a European Union-funded project that seeks to improve cancer prevention and early detection among experiencing homelessness people in Europe.
- <https://www.prolepsis.gr/gr/news/oloklirothike-to-2o-partners-meeting-gia-to-europaiko-programma-cancerless>: This page provides information on the second partners meeting of the Cancerless project, which is a European Union-funded project that seeks to improve cancer prevention and early detection among experiencing homelessness people in Europe.

- <https://www.proleptis.gr/gr/news/dimosieutike-to-blog-ianouariou-tou-europaikou-programmatos-cancerless>: This page provides information on the January blog post of the Cancerless project, which is a European Union-funded project that seeks to improve cancer prevention and early detection among experiencing homelessness people in Europe.
- <https://www.proleptis.gr/gr/news/to-institouto-proleptis-sto-22nd-international-conference-on-integrated-care-sti-dania>: This page provides information on the 22nd International Conference on Integrated Care held in Denmark, where the Proleptis Institute was represented by the Cancerless project.
- <https://www.proleptis.gr/gr/news/epistoli-tis-koinopraxias-tou-cancerless-kai-tou-diktuou-feantsa-stin-europaiki-epitropi>: This page provides information on the joint letter sent by the Cancerless project and the FEANTSA network to the European Commission, which seeks to promote cancer prevention and early detection among experiencing homelessness people in Europe.
- https://www.proleptis.gr/gr/news/world_human_rights_day_2022: This page provides information on World Human Rights Day 2022 and the international campaign being organised by the Cancerless project.
- https://www.proleptis.gr/gr/news/october_breast_cancer_awareness_month: This page provides information on Breast Cancer Awareness Month and the activities being organised by the Cancerless project.
- <https://www.facebook.com/ProleptisInstitute/posts/pfbid02EGZN2UZoeBztr3doRrq6YLmcSDSMoXHNyLQbftXi7dtX1jiofQooRCTgdphjWNqXl>: This page provides information on the activities of the Cancerless project, which is part of the Proleptis Institute.
- <https://www.feantsa.org/en/newsletter/2022/01/05/health-and-homelessness-newsletter-winter-2021?bcParent=27>: This page provides information on the winter 2021 edition of the Health and Homelessness Newsletter, which includes updates on the Cancerless project.
- <https://www.meduniwien.ac.at/web/ueber-uns/news/news-im-februar-2021/igor-grabovac-koordiniert-eu-projekt-zur-krebspraevention-und-optimierung-der-gesundheitsversorgung-obdachloser-menschen-in-europa/>:

This page provides information on Igor Grabovac, the project coordinator of the Cancerless project, and his role in coordinating the European Union-funded project that seeks to improve cancer prevention and early detection among experiencing homelessness people in Europe.

- <https://www.meduniwien.ac.at/web/en/ueber-uns/news/neews-im-februar-2021/igor-grabovac-koordiniert-eu-projekt-zur-krebspraevention-und-optimierung-der-gesundheitsversorgung-obdachloser-menschen-in-europa/>:

This page provides information on Igor Grabovac, the project coordinator of the Cancerless project, and his role in coordinating the European Union-funded project that seeks to improve cancer prevention and early detection among experiencing homelessness people in Europe.

- <https://www.prolepis.gr/gr/news/%cf%84%ce%bf-%ce%b9%ce%bd%cf%83%cf%84%ce%b9%cf%84%ce%bf%cf%8d%cf%84%ce%bf-prolepis-%cf%83%cf%84%ce%b7-%ce%bc%ce%b1%ce%b4%cf%81%ce%af%cf%84%ce%b7-%ce%b3%ce%b9%ce%b1-%cf%84%ce%bf-4o-partners-meeting/>: Prolepis

Website (news section - On the occasion of 4th Partners Meeting)

- <https://www.prolepis.gr/gr/news/%cf%80%ce%b1%ce%b3%ce%ba%cf%8c%cf%83%ce%bc%ce%b9%ce%b1-%ce%b7%ce%bc%ce%ad%cf%81%ce%b1-%cf%85%ce%b3%ce%b5%ce%af%ce%b1%cf%82-2023/>: Prolepis Website

(news section - On the occasion of the World Health Day 2023)

- <https://www.feantsa.org/en/feantsa-position/2023/11/29/>: FEANTSA launched a short Campaign on AMR and the threat it poses to people experiencing homelessness. This was achieved by informative postings on SM channels of FEANTA to show case Cancerless project. In addition we also launched a statement paper on "Antimicrobial Resistance and Homelessness" on our website to generate broad understanding of this threat and how this could impact the landscape of public health across Europe.
- <https://www.meduniwien.ac.at/web/en/ueber-uns/news/2024/news-im-februar-2024/improving-cancer-prevention-among-people-experiencing-homelessness-1/>: Post about an article published by the project.

- <https://www.itaca.upv.es/cancerless-empowering-the-homeless-in-the-fight-against-cancer/>: u team from the UPV participates in a European project for Early Cancer Diagnosis and Overcoming Healthcare Disparities Among Homeless Populations
- <https://igorgrabovac.com/research/our-projects/cancerless/>: the Grabovac Group is a research group (the Community Health Lab) based at the Department of Social and Preventive Medicine, Centre for Public health, Medical University of Vienna. We are a multidisciplinary team that is passionate about creating healthier and more just communities based on implementation science and following the principles of social medicine.
- <https://praksis.gr/cancerless-20-3-2024/>: Post about the meeting in Brussels organized by FEANTSA with the member of European Parliament St. Kypouropoulos
- <https://praksis.gr/cancerless-8-3-2024/>: Presentation of results achieved with the integration of the Health Navigator Model at PRAKSIS facilities
- <https://praksis.gr/cancerless-8-2-2024/> Post for meeting in Valencia regarding the completion of the Health Navigator Model.
- <https://praksis.gr/cancerless-28-5-23/>: Post about the Cancerless meeting in Athens hosted by Prolepsis Institute and PRAKSIS
- <https://praksis.gr/cancerless-navigator/>: Post about the meeting in Madrid about the Co-adapting and implementing the Health Navigator Model.
- <https://praksis.gr/cancerless-pr1/>: The CANCERLESS project aims to deliver an innovative solution as an aggregate intervention based on the combination of the tested Patient Navigator Model and Patient Empowerment Model to create the Health Navigator Model for Europe.

4.12. Social media activity conducted by partners

The partners' social media activity for the CANCERLESS project has been instrumental in promoting its mission and objectives both nationally, European and internationally. They have used a variety of platforms, from Twitter/X and Instagram to LinkedIn and

Facebook, to disseminate information about the project, participate in relevant events and raise awareness about the importance of addressing homeless health (please see Table 8).

Through managing and updating profiles, posting targeted content and participating in conferences and meetings, partners have demonstrated significant commitment to the cause. Their social media activity has enabled them to reach diverse audiences and generate interest in the project, thus contributing to its visibility and reach in both the national and international community.

In short, an active social media presence has been an effective tool for connecting with diverse audiences, sharing relevant information and advancing CANCERLESS' goals in the fight against cancer and inequalities in access to care.

Table 11 - Social media activity conducted by partners

Partner	Date	Title	Details	Countries addressed	URL
KVC	Whole project	Management and update of the Twitter profile	Twitter profile	International	https://twitter.com/CANCERLESS_EU
KVC	Whole project	Management and update of the Instagram profile	Instagram profile	International	https://www.instagram.com/cancerless_eu/
MADRID	2022	Cancerless Madrid	LinkedIn	National /pilot site	https://www.linkedin.com/company/87378813/admin/
UVEG	17/06/2021	Launch of the CANCERLESS project	Social media: Twitter	National	https://twitter.com/Polibienestar/status/1405441332269699073
PRAKSIS	17/06/2021	Post for project beginning "PRAKSIS participates in the Cancerless project"	Facebook	National	https://www.facebook.com/ngopraksis/posts/pfbid0hQSKtJePKm1RmJXXd3UW

					mAz5aYPAyfcoy wYysqQ4tqiGzA VAoKk9FE4wuq zbXsywl
UVEG	29/06/20 21	Conoce un poco más sobre el proyecto @CANCERLESS_EU, un proyecto destinado a la prevención y tratamiento del #cáncer dirigido a las personas sin hogar.	Social media: Twitter	National	https://twitter.com/Polibienestar/status/1409783548278624259
UVEG	22/07/20 21	Today the @CANCERLESS_EU team meets with the EU project officer to present the first steps of the project.	Social media: Twitter	International	https://twitter.com/Polibienestar/status/1418208404867223570
UPV	24/11/20 21	BDSL Lab Cancerless' presentation	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn, university	International	https://twitter.com/BDSLlab_UPV/status/1463538368051097600
IFIC	10/01/20 22	 https://bit.ly/3K8GbSD	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1480560277083070467
IFIC	17/01/20 22	Want to learn more about the @CANCERLESS_EU Project? CANCERLESS' vision is to prevent cancer and allow for early diagnoses in the homeless population by delivering person-centred interventions to overcome health inequalities LEARN MORE here	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1483041307949940737

		https://cancerless.eu/what-is-cancerless/			
PROLEPSIS	28/01/2022	2nd Partners Meeting	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	National	https://www.facebook.com/Prolepsisinstitute/posts/pfbid0vFkEAnf3mdaAw7n11hqi72BdyHZFLyqV6ggoFmAjS6SecfW64jjjW9d9tXTaYpnfl
PROLEPSIS	28/01/2022	2nd Partners Meeting	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	National	https://www.instagram.com/p/CZRs-sIKssq/
PROLEPSIS	28/01/2022	January's Blog	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	National	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/prolepsisinstitute_cancerless-prolepsisinstitute-commitmenttopublichealth-activity-6893815020526866432-cAEo?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
PROLEPSIS	28/01/2022	January's Blog	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	National	https://twitter.com/_Prolepsis/status/1488050061825220610
PROLEPSIS	29/01/2022	January's Blog	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	National	https://www.facebook.com/Prolepsisinstitute/posts/pfbid02PAU5q7aF6nMLzuk7kVWMru5wSSjCroGZQvG6

					Bay1vaPgKYKZG WcbjKbRNfNnqsNsl
PROLEPSIS	29/01/20 22	January's Blog	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	National	https://www.instagram.com/p/CZTuRDGo2BT/
IFIC	02/02/20 22	 https://cancerless.eu/homeless-covid-19-migrants/	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1488925430447026176
FEANTSA	03/02/20 22	Creating a project page on FEANTSA website and promoting it on social media	Social media and FEANTSA website;	European Union	https://www.feantsa.org/en/project/2022/02/03/the-cancerless-project?bcParent=418
FEANTSA	04/02/20 22	Promotion of the project on the World Cancer Day	Social media and FEANTSA website;	European Union	https://twitter.com/FEANTSA/status/1489531678502629380 ; https://www.feantsa.org/en/project/2022/02/03/the-cancerless-project?bcParent=418
IFIC	04/02/20 22	Today is #WorldCancerDay @CANCERLESS_EU project aims at overcoming #health inequalities by promoting quality cancer prevention & screening services for experiencing	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1489559508196241414

		homelessness people Find out more here https://cancerless.eu #WorldCancerDay2022 #CloseTheCareGap			
	04/02/2022	 https://cancerless.eu #WorldCancerDay2022 #CloseTheCareGap	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1489559508196241414
PROLEPSIS	04/02/2022	World Cancer DAY 2022	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	National	https://www.facebook.com/ProlepsisInstitute/posts/pfbid0QaNky6tGyBLrzQsJAzQiHkB2mKq1b1yrdWaAobECd2j5gwctwzynyhzJ5Uba4juxl
PROLEPSIS	04/02/2022	World Cancer DAY 2022	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	National	https://www.instagram.com/p/CZje-3KBJW/
PROLEPSIS	04/02/2022	World Cancer DAY 2022	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	National	https://twitter.com/_Prolepsis/status/1489572008060989442

UPV	04/02/20 22	Days against cancer	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn, university	International	https://twitter.com/BDSLlab_UPV/status/1489567160506671107
FEANTSA	16/02/20 22	FEANTSA and the CANCERLESS consortium call on the European Commission to include 'housing situation' as one of the inequality dimensions of the EU Cancer Registry	Direct communication with DG SANTE, Social media: Twitter Facebook; LinkedIn, FEANTSA website	European Union	https://twitter.com/FEANTSA/status/1493905314948730882
IFIC	18/02/20 22	@FEANTSA and the @CANCERLESS_EU consortium call on the European Commission to include 'housing situation' as one of the inequality dimensions of the EU Cancer Registry Learn more here https://bit.ly/3H2Dsad	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1494734142193422338
PROLEPSIS	18/02/20 22	Letter from the CANCERLESS Consortium and the FEANTSA Network to the European Commission	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn		https://www.facebook.com/ProlepsisInstitute/posts/pfbid0S8UVDYBSITHvHnobRbpXKETrB9sH3FziipRAs3ARAshcxGRdgMHgweob2o1AGktQI
UPV	21/02/20 22	Social Justice Day	Social media: Twitter;	International	https://twitter.com/BDSLlab_UPV/status/1495687908430430208

			Facebook; LinkedIn, university		
UPV	21/02/20 22	Social Justice Day	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn, university	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6901458751627612160
IFIC	03/03/20 22	What is @CANCERLESS_EU ? Reports note that cancer-related mortality is twice as high in the homeless population. CANCERLESS' vision is to prevent cancer and allow for early diagnoses in the homeless population. Learn more here 👇 https://bit.ly/3HFL3Mm	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1499424376671899656
IFIC	11/03/20 22	Joining #FollowFriday to highlight some of the amazing projects that we are involved in. If you would like to learn more about initiatives to prevent cancer in the European homeless population, give @CANCERLESS_EU a follow and check out their website: https://cancerless.eu 	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1502284010508242945
IFIC	18/03/20 22	Homelessness and women: a matter of visibility, a key to	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1504729596784173071

		cancer prevention. Read the full blog now 📄 https://bit.ly/3u339TL			
IFIC	10/04/20 22	Want to learn more about the @CANCERLESS_EU project? It aims to deliver an innovative solution as an aggregate intervention based on the combination of the tested Patient Navigator Model and Patient Empowerment Model. Learn more here 👉 https://bit.ly/3NP0eap	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1513094615561293829
IFIC	29/04/20 22	Today's #FOLLOWFRIDAY is @CANCERLESS_EU If you want to learn more about a project that aims to reduce the gap in health inequalities for the homeless population and reduce the cancer burden, check out the CANCERLESS website: https://cancerless.eu	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1519919607267659776
IFIC	04/05/20 22	'Social Determinants of Health' are non-medical factors intertwining the material circumstances of people, their socio-economic position and the socio-cultural environment as key mediators in their health status. Check @CANCERLESS_EU new blog 📄 https://bit.ly/3scYEpz	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1521775470370603009
IFIC	24/05/20 22	Busy workshop for IFIC's European Project team's Future of Integrated Care in the EU workshop at #ICIC22 #integratedcare	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1529091369326850053

PROLEPSIS	31/05/20 22	22nd International Conference on Integrated Care, Denmark	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	National	https://www.facebook.com/ProlepsisInstitute/posts/pfbid02EGZN2UZoeBztr3doRrq6YLmcSDSMoXHNyLQbftXi7dtX1jiofQooRC TgdphjWNqXI
PROLEPSIS	01/06/20 22	22nd International Conference on Integrated Care, Denmark	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	National	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6937324881244008448?updateEntityUrn=urn%3Ali%3As_feedUpdate%3A%28V2%2Curn%3Ali%3Aactivity%3A6937324881244008448%29
PROLEPSIS	01/06/20 22	22nd International Conference on Integrated Care, Denmark	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn	National	https://twitter.com/_Prolepsis/status/1531563599558111232
IFIC	08/07/20 22	<p>🗣️ Today's #FOLLOWFRIDAY is @CANCERLESS_EU</p> <p>Learn more about a project that aims to reduce the gap in health inequalities for the homeless population and reduce the cancer burden, check out the CANCERLESS website: https://cancerless.eu</p> <p>#euproject #IntegratedCare</p>	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	<i>International</i>	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1545377936471203840
FEANTSA	15/09/20 22	Blog article on 'Housing as a health determinant'	Social media: Twitter,	European Union	https://twitter.com/FEANTSA/status

			Instagram, Facebook; LinkedIn, FEANTSA website		s/1570675607989780481
FEANTSA	29/09/2022	CANCERLESS meeting Athens	Social media: Twitter, Instagram, Facebook;	European Union	https://twitter.com/FEANTSA/status/1575470185980518400
FEANTSA	03/10/2022	CANCERLESS visit at PRAKSIS	Social media: Twitter, Instagram, Facebook;	European Union	https://www.instagram.com/p/CjQGYxbD7nD/?hl=en
PRAKSIS	05/10/2022	Repost from FEANTSA "For the closing of our transnational meeting the Cancerless Project team visited the Praksis day centre in Athens for people experiencing #homelessness "	Facebook	National	https://www.facebook.com/ngopraksis/posts/pfbid02J6di4TdtXuWmiWrGF49xgTt5YVvw3uhJA3hGdnrqdod12H8WZyoxg8KZPU6LnWhl
IFIC	04/11/2022	We are hosting a @CANCERLESS_EU Webinar to spread awareness on the project and the CANCERLESS' vision to prevent cancer and allow for early diagnoses in the homeless population. 📅 Friday, 2 December 12pm - 1.30pm (IST) Learn more and register ➡ https://bit.ly/3hdIDON	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1588491258997215238

IFIC	04/11/2022	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	Twitter	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7004066701067567105/
IFIC	04/11/2022	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	LinkedIn	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7004066701067567105/
IFIC	11/11/2022	Our colleague Alejandro Gil-Salmerón @alejandrogalm presented on the @CANCERLESS_EU project today at @EPHconference #EPH2022. Great opportunity to spread awareness about the project and the work being conducted by partners.	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1591122274417090563
IFIC	11/11/2022	CANCERLESS Project presented by Alejandro of IFIC at EPH Conference	Twitter	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1588491258997215238
IFIC	15/11/2022	@CANCERLESS_EU A webinar will be held to spread awareness of the project. 📅 Friday, 2 December 12 pm - 1.30 pm (Irish Standard Time) Learn more and register ➡ https://bit.ly/3hdIDON @Kveloce_I_D_i @FEANTSA @UPV @ProleptisACLAMS @praksisgr @AngliaRuskin	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1592502849824772097
IFIC	15/11/2022	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	Twitter	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6

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Cancer prevention and early detection among the homeless population in Europe: Co-adapting and implementing the Health Navigator model

					994256812761870337/
IFIC	15/11/2022	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	LinkedIn	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6996887965918449664/
IFIC	23/11/2022	<p>We are hosting a @CANCERLESS_EU Webinar!</p> <p>Learn more about the project's initiative to eliminate inaccessibility to health care</p> <p>📅 Friday, 2 December 12pm - 1.30pm (IST)</p> <p>Register now ➔ https://bit.ly/3hdIDON</p> <p>@Kveloce_I_D_i @FEANTSA @UPV @_Proleptis @praksisgr @AngliaRuskin</p>	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1595371644381696000
UPV	23/11/2022	IFIC Webminar	Social media: Twitter; Facebook; LinkedIn, university	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7001219582698885121
IFIC	23/11/2022	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	Twitter	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1592502849824772097
IFIC	23/11/2022	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	LinkedIn	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6998268512506937344/
IFIC	28/11/2022	🚩 We are hosting a @CANCERLESS_EU	Social Media:	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status

		<p>Webinar!</p> <p>Addressing Fragmented Health and Accessibility of Cancer and Care Systems for people experiencing homelessness.</p> <p> Friday, 2 December</p> <p> 12pm - 1.30pm (Irish Standard Time)</p> <p>Learn more and register</p> <p> https://bit.ly/3hdIDON</p>	Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook		/1597213822124576769
IFIC	28/11/2022	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	Twitter	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1595371644381696000
IFIC	28/11/2022	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	LinkedIn	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7001137418925973504/
IFIC	30/11/2022	<p>@CANCERLESS_EU Webinar Speaker Announcement!</p> <p>@alejandrosalm will present on 'CANCERLESS blueprint for integrated cancer care: tackling healthcare inequalities in Europe'. Join us!</p> <p> Friday, 2 December</p> <p> 12pm - 1.30pm IST, 1pm - 2.30pm CET</p> <p>Register now https://bit.ly/3hdIDON</p>	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1597943753574055936
FEANTSA	30/11/2022	CANCERLESS webinar promotion	Social media: Twitter,	European Union	https://twitter.com/CANCERLESS_EU/status/159788

			Instagram, Facebook; LinkedIn, FEANTSA website, FEANTSA health newsletter		3990685675520: https://www.instagram.com/stories/highlights/17976319729675365/?hl=en
IFIC	30/11/2022	@CANCERLESS_EU Webinar Update! @LisLehner @MedUni_Wien will present on 'Lived experience of a Health Navigator working with people experiencing homelessness – Austrian Case'. 📅 Friday, 2nd December 🕒 12pm - 1.30pm IST, 1pm - 2.30pm CET Register now ➡ https://bit.ly/3hdIDON	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1597972306898329603
IFIC	30/11/2022	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	Twitter	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1597213822124576769
IFIC	30/11/2022	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	Twitter	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7002979457024020482/
IFIC	30/11/2022	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	LinkedIn	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1597972306898329603
IFIC	30/11/2022	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	LinkedIn	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1597943753574055936

IFIC	01/12/20 22	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	LinkedIn	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7004066701067567105/
IFIC	01/12/20 22	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	LinkedIn	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7003737998550814720/
IFIC	02/12/20 22	Taking last-minute registrations for our @CANCERLESS_EU webinar! Join us for Pania Karnaki @_Proleptis ' presentation on the Pilot Implementation of the Health Navigator Model in Real-Life Settings 📅 TODAY 12pm - 1.30pm IST, 1pm - 2.30pm CET Register → https://bit.ly/3hdIDON	Social Media: Twitter, LinkedIn & Facebook	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1598588198971936768
IFIC	02/12/20 22	Marketing Campaign for CANCERLESS Webinar by IFIC	LinkedIn	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7004066701067567105/
PRAKSIS	24/03/20 23	Pilot implementation of the Health Navigator Model	Facebook	National	https://www.facebook.com/ngopraksis/posts/pfbid0cUJnNYsxqSEyuhgoPgAvKhpV5du7CBST68aT8ebfMiufyJUzZDEZxH9g8vfWTzzul
SERMAS	05/06/20 23	Creation of the LinkedIn profile for the Spanish Pilot	LinkedIn	National	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cancerless-madrid/
SERMAS	13/06/20 23	LinkedIn post announcing the presentation of the	LinkedIn	National	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7004066701067567105/

		CANCERLESS project at the WONCA conference			ate/urn:li:activity:7073991481954377728/
IFIC	15.06.2023	IFIC presented on CANCERLESS at EHMA.	Twitter	International	https://twitter.com/IFICInfo/status/1669253772311248896
PROLEPSIS	22/06/2023	Pilot implementation of the Health Navigator Model in real-life settings	Instagram	National	https://www.instagram.com/p/CtypuuwKZhE/
PROLEPSIS	22/06/2023	Pilot implementation of the Health Navigator Model in real-life settings	Facebook	National	https://www.facebook.com/Prolepsisinstitute/posts/pfbid02KjBD4DGSTBYFCGjGFtYvMqQnNbYHWEnM6SgCRuhgAxLxtJmKEjEjW4CX71QdGYYx!
PROLEPSIS	28/06/2023	Post about "the Athens Pilot"	Instagram	National	https://www.instagram.com/p/CuCVMOHKtbD/
UPV	12/07/2023	🇪🇺 El pasado viernes se celebró el #WIICT de @itacaUPV, donde @JMGG_BDSLlab fue galardonado 🏆 como mejor investigador del instituto. 🗣️ "Gracias a @InAdvance_eu, @CANCERLESS_EU, #Cocaptain, #Sinué, el proyecto con @GVA112 & #CSAMHealth y a todos los investigadores del BDSLab" 🙌🙌	Twitter	National	https://twitter.com/BDSLlab_UPV/status/1679062563626143744
IFIC	19.07.2023	IFIC created a cartoon video to explain what the project is about	Vimeo	International	https://vimeo.com/manage/videos/871111914

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	31/08 - 03/09/23	World Congress of Psycho- oncology	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram	International	
FEANTSA	20/09- 21/09/23	World Cancer Series	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram	International	
PROLEPSIS	26/09/20 23	5th Partners Meeting in Athens	X/Twitter	International	https://twitter.com/Prolepsis/status/1706588086157680888
FEANTSA	10/10/20 23	Mental Health Conference	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram	International	
KVC	19/10/20 23	Share the CANCERLESS Video	Twitter	International	https://twitter.com/CANCERLESS_EU/status/1714910236874514729
FEANTSA	08/11/20 23	Continenence Health Summit in Brussels	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram	International	
FEANTSA	09/11/20 23	European Economic and Social Committee	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram	International	
FEANTSA	15/11/23 - 16/11/23	European Cancer Summit	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram	International	
FEANTSA	17/11/20 23	Interact Europe	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram	International	
FEANTSA	21/11/20 23	Pancreatic Cancer Europe: Physical exercise and cancer	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram	International	
KVC	28/11/20 23	ERC Annual Conference 2023: Research on Diversity & Diversity in Frontier Research	Twitter	International	https://twitter.com/Kveloce_ID_i/status/1729524905572458998

KVC	28/11/20 23	ERC Annual Conference 2023: Research on Diversity & Diversity in Frontier Research	LinkedIn	International	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7135288330706894848
FEANTSA	29/11/20 23	A comprehensive approach to Mental Health- EU Parliament	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram		
FEANTSA	29/11/20 23	Men & cancer: Manifesto release ECO at EU parliament	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram		
FEANTSA	05/12/20 23	European Cancer Forum,	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram		
FEANTSA	06/12/20 23	Racism, discrimination, and health: a human rights-based approach-EPHA	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram		
FEANTSA	08/12/20 23	Universal access & Affordable medicine Forum: EPHA	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram		
FEANTSA	11/12/20 23	Accelerating Cancer Care in Europe	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram	International	
FEANTSA	01/01/20 24	World AIDS Day	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram	International	
FEANTSA	31/01/20 24	EU Commission-Europe's Beatings Cancer Plan Update	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram	International	
MUW	01/02/20 24	Interview with Igor Grabovac and Maren Jeleff for the review article published in the prestigious journal "The Lancet Public Health"	YouTube	International	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4NEkGPD4a4c

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MUW	01/02/20 24	Interview with Igor Grabovac and Maren Jeleff for the review article published in the prestigious journal "The Lancet Public Health"	Twitter	International	https://twitter.com/MedUni_Wien/status/1752986305259061723
PROLEPSIS	04/02/20 24	Post on the occasion of World Cancer Day	Facebook	International	https://www.facebook.com/ProleptisInstitute/posts/pfbid0hjzJ1zaeYFcH51KML4k3AQMF7C1ktvqjs33N6zjRc6VzDydfTCXCtLQSpnsxsVdHl
PROLEPSIS	04/02/20 24	Post on the occasion of World Cancer Day	Instagram	International	https://www.instagram.com/p/C263dAONTfw/
UPV	06/02/20 24	Participation in the meeting held in Valencia	X/Twitter and LinkedIn	International	https://twitter.com/BDSLlab_UPV/status/1754827575493267558
FEANTSA	05/02- 06/02/24	Cancerless Consortium Meeting	LinkedIn, FB, Twitter, Instagram	International	
PROLEPSIS	14/02/20 24	Participation in the meeting held in Valencia	Facebook	International	https://www.facebook.com/ProleptisInstitute/posts/pfbid02AaznfRqWJdUcwDy66LUFRkAWuPWkVsyr5Zz3MJAxWk1oVqjKjhhmuvt1NaVAmhZRI
PROLEPSIS	14/02/20 24	Participation in the meeting held in Valencia	Instagram	International	https://www.instagram.com/p/C3VFxddoYrx/

5. CONCLUSIONS

Communication and dissemination play essential role in the success and impact of any project, and the CANCERLESS Project is no exception. Throughout its development, a comprehensive communication strategy has been implemented to raise awareness of health inequalities and emphasize the importance of timely access to cancer prevention and screening services for the homeless population in Europe. These communication initiatives have been instrumental in achieving the project's objectives and effectively disseminating its results.

Scientific dissemination has also been a crucial aspect of project communication. Several scientific articles have been published in specialised journals and the project has participated in relevant scientific events and conferences to share its findings and results of the project with the scientific and academic community. This scientific dissemination has allowed the project's achievements to be validated and shared with experts in the field, thereby reinforcing its credibility and relevance.

Throughout the project, a range of printed materials have been produced to enhance the project's visibility at events, conferences and other relevant settings. Brochures, posters and roll-ups have provided key information about the project and helped raise awareness of health inequalities and the importance of access to cancer prevention and screening services.

One of the main communication tools has been the project website. This site has been designed as a central source of information about CANCERLESS, providing full details of the project's objectives, activities and results. Throughout the implementation period, the website has been regularly updated with news, updates and events related to the project, thus keeping the audience informed and engaged.

In addition to the website, social media has been a key component of the project's communication strategy. Platforms such as Instagram and Twitter/X have been utilized to share news, events and other content related to CANCERLESS, reaching a wider audience and encouraging public participation in the project's activities. Interaction on

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social media has allowed for greater visibility and reach of the project, significantly contributing to its impact.

Despite the achievements, areas for improvement have been identified.. The involvement of certain stakeholders, such as health professionals and decision-makers, could have been more active and continuous monitoring is required to fully evaluate and understand the impact of the communication and dissemination activities.

The CANCERLESS Project's dissemination and communication strategy has been essential to meet the project's main objective: to raise awareness of health inequalities and facilitate access to cancer prevention and screening services for the homeless population in Europe. Through a wide range of activities and communication channels, the project has reached a diverse audience and effectively disseminated its results and impact.. This comprehensive strategy has not only contributed to the success of the project, but also highlighted its relevance in the European public health arena, thus strengthening the commitment to the health and well-being of all citizens, especially those in vulnerable situations.

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